

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D5.4 – Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 1

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>This report, part of the UP2030 project, presents a comprehensive needs assessment, including literature review and engagement with pilot cities, to identify key barriers European cities face in conducting economic assessments and obtaining finance for their climate actions. It details the ongoing development of the Green Finance Guide and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) Guide—two tools designed to help cities implement and upscale climate actions towards a just, resilient, and climate-neutral transition. The Green Finance Guide offers a comprehensive overview of financial instruments and strategies to secure finance, while the CBA Guide provides guidance for assessing the economic viability of climate projects and investments. As the project advances, efforts will focus on refining these Guides, incorporating city feedback, and integrating them into the UP2030 Service Platform.</p>			

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Executive summary

Average temperatures across Europe are rising faster than the global average, and Europe's cities are feeling the impacts of climate change more regularly and more severely. The impacts of climate change can be even more intensely felt in urban areas due to their morphology and their dense infrastructure and population. They take up only 4% of the European Union's (EU) land area and are home to 75% of EU citizens. On a global scale, cities consume over 65% of the world's energy and account for more than 70% of global CO₂ emissions, placing cities at the forefront of climate change action.

UP2030 aims to support cities in facilitating the socio-technical transitions necessary to achieve their carbon neutrality goals: At the heart of the project, the innovative 5UP approach (Update, Upskill, Upgrade, Upscale, and Uptake) actively engages cities and their stakeholders through five interlocked phases to implement climate actions. Within UP2030, Work Package (WP) 5 "UP-SCALING – Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making" focuses on extending climate solutions across scales and integrating them across sectors by shaping governance arrangements and financial mechanisms. While also responding to a new cycle of needs assessment, to understand which processes, planning codes and policies should be urgently updated, identifying and addressing needs and barriers (as per the Update phase).

One of WP5's objectives is to develop guides for cities on green finance and cost-benefit analysis (CBA) to support them to overcome specific financial barriers. This document reports on the progress made on the guides that the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) is preparing, whilst providing an overview of cities' needs and barriers towards financing their climate action. The report targets cities' practitioners and decision-makers, as well as project partners of the UP2030 project and the broader public. This includes other European cities not directly involved in the project but interested in using the guides to prepare their own economic assessments and mobilize resources for climate action.

The document is structured into six main parts. The first section provides an introduction to the report, outlining the purpose and scope of the document, with a glossary of the most relevant terms used in the report. Section 2 provides the project context, presenting the UP2030 initiative and the role of finance and CBA in supporting cities to upscale their climate action. Both sections set the foundations for understanding the subsequent sections of the document: cities' barriers and needs assessment and the introduction of the Green Finance Guide and CBA Guide that GGGI is developing to aid on finance and CBA to cities under Task 5.3 "Financing the transition" (T5.3).

Cities have the potential to achieve climate neutrality and resilience but face significant barriers to financing their climate action. Section 3 explores these barriers. The first part of the section introduces the literature on financing barriers and needs for cities' climate action. The second part presents findings from pilot city engagements, including workshops and surveys, highlighting specific challenges and needs in accessing and utilizing finance for climate projects. The literature identifies regulatory constraints, high municipal debt, and low creditworthiness, as significant barriers to accessing finance. Private investment is limited by high upfront costs and complex procurement processes. Legal frameworks often restrict municipalities from accessing certain financing mechanisms. Additionally, cities struggle with preparing investor-ready projects and face competing national priorities. The section also summarises the results of direct engagement with pilot cities of the UP2030 project, through surveys and workshops, providing valuable insights into their specific financing needs and barriers. Cross-cutting themes from all pilot city engagements include the need for unlocking finance from various sources, integrated financial strategies and better coordination within city departments to reduce the impact of organisational silos. The needs assessments emphasise the overall lack of funding available at city levels to finance climate action and the

necessity to explore and tap into diverse funding sources. There is also a need for improved communication and collaboration internally and externally with stakeholders (e.g., private financiers), and the ability to demonstrate cost-benefit justifications for climate projects to implement climate initiatives effectively.

Section 4 on green finance introduces the Green Finance Guide tool GGGI is developing to help cities scale up green finance through the identification and utilisation of suitable financial instruments and models for green projects. First, the section presents the tool objectives, explains the specific financing needs that the tool addresses, matches tool solutions to financing needs, and explains the value added of the tool to be developed against existing tools. Second, the section details the content of the tool. It provides an overview of the financial instruments that are available for cities and that will be included in the tool. The section then explains how these instruments will be classified and filtered – based on their degree of innovation, climate objective, source of funds, risk-return relationship, etc. – for cities to identify and evaluate their suitability. Ensuite, the section also explains how the Green Finance Guide supports cities in leveraging private finance. It provides case examples that exemplify the combined utilisation of financial instruments and economic incentives, as well as the creation of financing models where multiple financial instruments interact. Finally, the section explains the role of the different financial stakeholders for cities' findings. It also lists providers of finance for cities per sector as well as providers of technical assistance for cities to support the ideation, development, and implementation of green projects.

On CBA, section 5 provides a high-level guidance for cities to evaluate the economic viability of climate projects, emphasising its importance in climate policy and decision-making. It highlights the need to assess both monetary and non-monetary benefits, such as public health improvements and environmental quality. The section also offers an overview of existing CBA tools and methodologies. To further assist cities, the section introduces the CBA Guide GGGI is developing on cost-benefit assessments, which simplifies the selection and application of appropriate CBA tools tailored to the specific needs and capacities of cities. This guide provides detailed instructions on using existing CBA tools based on cities' specific needs, focusing on practical implementation and addressing challenges like quantifying non-tangible benefits and filling data gaps.

Section 6 summarises this report. Both the Green Finance Guide and CBA Guide are under development and this report presents their current status and outlines the next steps for further refinement and implementation steps: Ongoing refinement and finalisation, integrating the guides onto the UP2030 Service Platform (T5.2), and examining further development needs, based on city feedback through a planned workshop with cities during the second UP2030 General Assembly (GenA) in M22 (October 15-17, 2024). These steps aim to ensure that the guides remain practical, user-friendly, and tailored to the most pressing needs of cities in their pursuit of climate neutrality and resilience. By the end of the project, cities will have access to interactive web-based Green Finance and CBA Guides available on the UP2030 Service Platform.

[Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables](#)

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the WP structures. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with WP5 leaders and task leaders from WP5, WP2, and the Strategy and Learning Taskforce. The following table lists the deliverables (D) and milestones (Mil.) that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
<p>D2.1 The 5UP approach and its contextualization in the project cities.</p> <p>D2.2, D2.3 UP2030 benchmarking report against state-of-the-art and identification of pilot opportunities (1 and 2)</p> <p>D2.5 Report on vision co-design methodology and its application for pilot shared visions</p> <p>D5.1 Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 1</p>	<p>D3.2 Transformative Pathways Roadmaps: Strategic Integration of Solutions and Interoperability 2</p> <p>D5.2 Analysis and recommendations for transformative governance and policy 2</p> <p>D5.3 UP2030 Service platform</p> <p>D5.5 Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 2</p>
<p>Mil.5 Cities run first workshop on needs</p> <p>Mil.6 Cities run second workshop on vision</p>	<p>Mil.10 Cities run third workshop on action</p> <p>Mil.14 Cities run second workshop on upscale</p> <p>Mil.16 Service platform up operative</p>

This deliverable is a progress report on the guides GGGI is preparing for cities on economic valuations and on financial instruments. The report aims to provide information to UP2030 partners and European cities (UP2030 pilot cities and beyond) with an overview on cities' barriers and needs in relation to funding and financing instruments and mechanism (collectively, green finance), cost and benefit assessment and existing CBA tools available for cities. At the same time the report also provides an update on the progress on two guides GGGI is developing (i) the Green Finance Guide on financial measures (financial instruments, sources of finance and funding) and (ii) a CBA Guide. The next, final report due on M32, "D5.5 Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 2" will present the fully developed guides. The guides will be hosted on the UP2030 Service platform (D5.3).

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AFD	French Development Agency (Agence Française de Développement)
bot	build-operate-transfer
BwB	Bankers Without Boundaries
CAF	Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean
CAPEX	capital expenditures
CBA	Cost-Benefit analysis
CCFLA	Cities Climate Finance Leadership Alliance
CDP	The Carbon Disclosure Project
CFF	Cities Finance Facility
CPI	Climate Policy Institute
CTF	Clean Technology Fund
D	Deliverable
EBRD	European Development for Reconstruction and Development
ECB	European Central Bank
eft	ecological fiscal transfers
EIB	European Investment Bank
EPC	Energy performance contracts
ESCO	Energy Service Companies
ESG	Environmental, social, and governance
ETF	Exchange-traded fund
ETS	Emissions trading system
EU	European Union

EV	Electric vehicle
FS	Frankfurt School of Finance and Management
GCF	Green Climate Fund
GenA	General Assembly
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GIF	Global Infrastructure Facility
ICA	Inclusive Climate Action
ICAT	Initiative for Climate Action Transparency
ICF	UK's International Climate Finance Initiative
IFC	International Finance Corporation
IKI	Germany's International Climate Initiative
IP	2030 Climate Neutrality Investment Plan
JCM	Joint Crediting Mechanism
KfW	German Credit Institute for Reconstruction (Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau)
LVC	Land value capture
M	Month
MDB	Multilateral Development Bank
Mil.	Milestone
NAP	National Adaptation Plan
NZC	NetZeroCities
ODA	Official Development Assistance
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OEKB	Austrian Development Bank (Oesterreichische Kontrollbank Aktiengesellschaft)
OPEX	operational expenditures

OSR	Own source revenues
PDB	Public development banks
PM	particulate matter
PPF	Project Preparation Facility
PPP	Public-private partnerships
RDI	Research, development and innovation
SCF	Strategic Climate Fund
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
T	Task
TA	Technical assistance
TAF	Technical Assistance Facility
TAP	Transformative Actions Program
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TUD	Delft University of Technology
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of Task 5.3 "Financing the transition" is to help cities to upscale their climate interventions by developing guidance for cities to conduct economic assessments and to identify financial measures and instruments available to them to mobilise finance. The primary objective of this document is to help European cities enhance their climate action efforts by providing guidance:

1. To mobilise financial measures (instruments and sources): To inform cities about available financing and funding sources, offering practical guidance on leveraging different financial instruments to secure the necessary funds for their climate initiatives.
2. On conducting Cost-Benefit analysis (CBA): To provide cities with a guide for assessing the costs and benefits of various climate interventions. Due to considerable availabilities of various CBA tools, the project develops a CBA Guide to support cities employ the appropriate CBA tool with supporting documents and data sources.

To support the achievement of these two key objectives, the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) is developing two practical guides (a) Green Finance Guide and (b) CBA Guide that can match cities' needs to the recommended solutions. To lay the groundwork for the development of the guides GGGI's project team conducted a needs assessment of cities (through UP2030 city needs assessments under WP2 and through financing and CBA targeted surveys and workshops, see section 3.2), supported by a general literature review, of which the results are presented in the report. This structured approach ensures that the tools are theoretically grounded and tailored to the real needs of cities. The report also offers a comprehensive theoretical background on available financing instruments, mechanisms, and funding sources essential for scaling up climate interventions in urban areas (Objective 1). Additionally, it outlines the structure of the tool that GGGI is developing to map these instruments and guide the cities according to their needs (**Green Finance Guide**). This Guide details the benefits and shortcomings of various financing options and provides guidance to cities on relevant stakeholders who provide financing or technical assistance. Moreover, it also guides cities in developing robust business cases to secure funding by showcasing innovative instruments and blending of different financial instruments and mechanisms. Finally, the report introduces the CBA methodology for conducting economic assessment (Objective 2), existing tools. It also presents the tool GGGI is developing that cities can use to select the CBA tool that suits their needs best and perform detailed CBA, essential for informed decision-making (**CBA Guide**). Both guides are under development and the sections presenting them provides readers with a status, outputs, outcomes, impacts expected, and next steps for implementation. By the end of the project, cities will have access to interactive web-based Green Finance and CBA Guides available on the T5.2 Service Platform. Cities will first familiarise themselves with the Guides in the upcoming UP2030 General Assembly (GenA) in M22 (October 15-17, 2024).

1.2 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 – Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure and a glossary.
- ❖ Section 2 – Background: on project context.

- ❖ Section 3 – Cities' financing barriers and needs: understanding barriers and challenges cities face in obtaining finance for urban climate interventions.
- ❖ Section 4 – Green finance: overview of funding and financing and economic instruments and mechanisms, overview of relevant stakeholders for financing and technical assistance to support green urban development as well as the introduction of the Green Finance Guide (under development), its expected outputs, impacts and next steps.
- ❖ Section 5 – Cost-benefit analysis: overview of CBA methodologies available for cities to use and the introduction of the CBA Guide (under development) on conducting cost benefit assessments, its expected outputs, impacts and next steps.
- ❖ Section 6 – Conclusion
- ❖ Section 7 – References
- ❖ Appendices

1.3 Glossary of terms used in this report

Bankability - refers to the willingness of financial institutions to finance a project or proposal. In other words, "bankable" means that a project has sufficient collateral, future cashflow and probability of success to be accepted for financing by a commercial bank or institutional financing (OECD, 2016).

Climate finance - is a subset of green finance, that aims at reducing emissions and enhancing sinks of greenhouse gases and aims at reducing vulnerability of, and maintaining and increasing the resilience of, human and ecological systems to negative climate change impacts (UNFCCC, 2023) (World Bank, 2023).

Cost-Benefit analysis (CBA) - is a tool for socio-economic appraisal and evaluation of public interventions. It is one of the major tools used to analyse the relative efficacy and effectiveness of interventions. It is designed to demonstrate whether or not the long-term social and environmental benefits of a project are greater than its costs (OECD, 2015).

Debt - instruments are agreements between a lender and a borrower in which the agreement lender receives fixed payment(s), usually with interest (National Adaptation Plan (NAP) Global Network and International Institute for Sustainable Development, 2024). Borrowing can be done through bonds or bank loans, or other sources. These borrowed funds can come either from a private or public source.

Economic assessment - is the process of evaluating and prioritising well-defined climate intervention options using economic criteria or criteria that can be included in economic analyses (GIZ, 2013). An economic assessment basically deals with the following: benefits and costs, often measured in monetary terms, and with efficiency and effectiveness serving as a sort of quotient or ratio of both cost and benefits.

Economic instruments - are fiscal and other economic incentives and disincentives to incorporate environmental costs and benefits into the households' and enterprises' budgets. These can include subsidies, taxes, charges or fiscal transfers (OECD, 2024)

Equity – is a type of financing that is the purchase of a share in the ownership of a company or project. It is often called shareholders' equity or owners' equity on a balance sheet, represents the amount of money that belongs to the owners of a business after all assets and liabilities have been accounted for (Landry, 2018)

Financial instruments - is an asset or evidence of the ownership of an asset, or a contractual agreement between two parties that can be created, traded, modified, and settled. They represent assets, liabilities, or equity and are used for raising capital, transferring risk, or investing (CFI, 2024).

Financing - refers to money from private or public financiers used to pay some or all of the up-front investment costs, which comes with an obligation for future repayment. In most countries, the 'golden rule' applies, meaning that financing for subnational governments is only permitted to cover investment needs and cannot be used to cover current expenditure (e.g. operating costs). Financing may be debt (loans, bonds) or equity, particularly in the case of a Public Private Partnership. Financing is repaid from funding sources (OECD, 2022).

Financing mechanisms - in international environmental law, they are ways and means of providing new and additional financial resources (UNEP, 1992).

Funding - refers to the money ultimately used to pay for an investment. It may come through various consolidated subnational government revenue sources (i.e. grants and subsidies, taxes, various user charges and fees, reserves, property income, etc.) or from a specific user-charge paid by a user to a public or private infrastructure operator (for example, under a concession agreement). While funding is not required to pay up-front investment costs, it is always required to pay for operations, maintenance, and the repayment of financing (OECD, 2022).

Green finance - is any structured financial activity – a product or service – that's been created to ensure a better environmental outcome (including climate change). It includes an array of loans, debt mechanisms and investments that are used to encourage the development of green projects or minimize the impact on the climate of more regular projects, or a combination of both (Fleming, 2020). In this report, "green finance" refers to the comprehensive set of economic and financial instruments, mechanisms, as well as financing and funding sources available to local governments and urban municipalities to obtain finance for their climate-related and other environmental interventions.

Innovative finance - includes mechanisms and solutions, which increase the volume, efficiency, and effectiveness of financial flows, that mobilise, govern, or distribute funds beyond official development assistance (ODA) (DESA- UNEN, 2021). Innovate finance solutions create scalable and effective ways of channelling both private money from the global and local financial markets and public resources towards sustainable investments.

Low-carbon - the term low-carbon or low-carbon development means reduction of carbon emission to minimal level to mitigate greenhouse gases responsible for global warming and climate change (UNDP, 2017).

Resilient - is the ability of a system and its component to anticipate, absorb, accommodate, or recover from the effects of a hazardous event in a timely and efficient manner, including through ensuring the preservation, restoration, or improvement of its essential basic structures and functions (IPCC, 2012).

Sustainable finance - is a term that describes the use of financial tools and strategies to achieve environmental and social goals. This type of financing considers environmental, social and governance (ESG) aspects when evaluating and making investment decisions. (UNEP, 2016)

2 Background

2.1 Project context

UP2030 is an innovative action project supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe program. UP2030 aims to support cities in driving the socio-technical transitions required to meet their climate neutrality targets by leveraging urban planning and design. Within the project, city stakeholders and local authorities are supported and guided to put neutrality and resilience on the map in their day-to-day actions and strategic decisions.

The UP2030 consortium comprises 10+1 cities: Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, and Zagreb, with Rio de Janeiro as an observer city. These pilot cities operationalize and co-develop the UP methodology and tools through their demonstration projects.

Figure 1: Pilot cities of the UP2030 HE project

2.2 The role of CBA and finance within UP2030

To achieve the objectives of the project an innovative methodology, the UP2030 project develops and applies the so-called 5UP-approach (Figure 2) for activating cities and their stakeholders through 5 interlinked phases and the co-development and implementation of science-based - yet practical - tools, and methods (UP2030 Project, 2023).

Figure 2: UP2030 methodological framework ("5UP")

- UP-dating, those policies, codes, and regulations that need to be left behind to make room for the new vision;
- UP-skilling, through building the capacities of the entire city stakeholder ecosystem that shall deliver actions;
- UP-grading, through the development of solution prototypes (digital and physical) at selected neighbourhoods;
- UP-scaling, to achieve city-wide impact by shaping the enabling governance arrangements and matching project portfolios to financial resources;
- UP-taking, by engaging with the EU Mission of Climate-Neutral and Smart cities (hereinafter EU Mission) and sharing best practices across European cities.

Within UP2030, the WP5, "UP-SCALING - Implementation and mainstreaming through renewed policy development and decision-making" focuses on extending the solutions across scales and integrating across sectors, whilst also responding to updating needs by shaping governance arrangements and financial mechanisms. The analysis of costs and benefits of climate action projects can significantly assist urban decision-makers in working out the best strategy for using scarce economic resources for the most effective climate measures and help prioritise and design climate investments. Moreover, it can raise awareness of the benefits of climate interventions and gain political and social support and improve its potential to obtain finance. Finance has a central role in enabling city-wide implementation and replication of cities' pilot and demonstration initiatives leading to a sustainable transition to a low-carbon, climate resilient future.

3 Cities' financing barriers and needs

3.1 Barriers to financing urban climate action

Average temperatures across Europe are rising faster than the global average, and Europe's cities are feeling the impacts of climate change more regularly and more severely (European Environment Agency, 2024). The impacts of climate change can be even more intensely felt in urban areas due to their morphology and their dense infrastructure and population (European Environment Agency, 2023). In addition to their unique vulnerability to climate change, European cities take up only 4% of the European Union's (EU) land area and are home to 75% of EU citizens. On a global scale, cities consume over 65% of the world's energy and account for more than 70% of global CO₂ emissions (European Commission, 2021), giving them a pivotal role in achieving climate neutrality and building resilience of urban systems. This places cities at the centre of both climate change adaptation and mitigation efforts. Yet at the same time, they face significant challenges in achieving low carbon and climate resilient development. Cities hold many capabilities and responsibilities needed for progress towards sustainability, but whether they fulfil their potential depends on raising finance for a significant expansion of low-emission climate-resilient infrastructure (Alexander et al., 2019). Large scale climate interventions require considerable resources to bring them into fruition. An estimated US\$93 trillion of sustainable infrastructure needs to be built by 2030 — more than 70 percent of which will be built in urban areas (World Bank, 2023). Urban infrastructure investment needs have been estimated at USD 4.5 – 5.4 trillion per year from 2015-2030, with a portion of this (10-25%) related to additional investment costs or incremental costs to ensure infrastructure is low emission and climate resilient (Negreiros et al., 2021). Research literature shows that accessing and attracting finance are some of the most significant barriers that cities face in delivering their climate change plans (C40 Cities, 2016). GGGI categorised these barriers into distinct type relying on a variety of sources (Hallmeyer & Tonkonogy, 2018), (CCFLA, 2015), (Alexander et al., 2019).

Financing barriers

Today's financing landscape does not provide cities with adequate access to affordable financing suited to low-emission, climate-resilient infrastructure. The challenge is not simply to increase the amount of money in the pipeline, but also to create an enabling environment that encourages existing and new financing to flow from a broad spectrum of sources (CCFLA, 2015). Local governments often have **budget capacity constraints** and are unable to finance the large volumes of low-carbon and climate resilient infrastructure needed to realise climate transitions.

Difficulty in **engaging with private investors** can be caused by **high levels of municipal debt** and **low rates of creditworthiness** or the absence of credit rating. Additionally, high upfront and, or maintenance costs, **capital costs hurdles** and no direct or quantifiable cost savings and **low return on investment** can all hinder the ability to obtain finance from private sources. High transaction costs, particularly from numerous small-scale investments, could also pose a significant barrier to attract private investors. **Information asymmetry** and insufficient familiarity and interaction between private actors and municipalities are significant causes of the lack of engagement. These issues can further exacerbate the problem in the future by increasing transaction costs, as private investors need to perform extra due diligence (C40 Cities, 2016) (CCFLA, 2015). The lack of ability or even willingness by private investors to assess the capital risks of a project can further reduce the chances of municipalities to leverage private finance (Alexander et al., 2019).

Market environment may also be unsupportive to sector-specific and general investment (e.g., lack of capital or lack of access to the right kinds of finance). Although projects may take place at the municipal

level, investors are also wary of the **risks at the country level**, including currency and exchange rate fluctuation, inflation, and political risk, none of which cities have control over (Carter & Boukerche, 2020). Risk sensitivity is problematic when attaining private finance, especially in economies where there are often higher levels of uncertainty over policies that influence the economics of investing, such as tax subsidies.

Lack of reliable funding streams lower the financial attractiveness of a project and the potential to tap into further sources of finance. Returns often rely on funding and government subsidies and policies and funding is essential to support infrastructure investment by subnational governments. Moreover, funding can help to pay up-front costs and is also required to pay operational and maintenance costs, which usually cannot be paid by financing. In the case where financing is leveraged to help meet up-front costs, funding also needs to be made available to repay financing in the future (OECD, 2022).

Limited taxation powers, increasing taxes could also be difficult in the current economic (and political) environment. Taxpayers are weary of having to provide any more funds following several years of overlapping negative shocks and record high inflation.

Multilateral and bilateral **development finance institutions** are another well-known source of finance, yet they are traditionally oriented to work at the **national rather than the municipal level**. Although they remain an important source of urban climate investment, they are not directly accessible to cities, which must go through national ministries, where tensions and competing priorities can arise (Alexander et al., 2019).

Legal and regulatory barriers

Legal and regulatory frameworks could also limit access to certain types of finance. **Regulatory debt limit** (including the issuance of municipal bonds) and regulation limits on borrowing by local governments (including issuance of municipal bonds). Regulation could also **limit the powers of municipalities** to raise funds, increase taxes or fines. Studies suggest that 56% of countries forbid any kind of borrowing by local governments (including the issuance of municipal bonds), and only 16% of countries allow any taxation powers (Negreiros et al., 2021). Most countries in Europe impose some form of regulatory or legal limits on local government borrowing and tax-raising abilities, typically requiring higher-level approval or adhering to strict regulations to ensure fiscal responsibility and prevent excessive debt accumulation (Geißler et al., 2019).

There could also be legal or regulatory **constraints on innovative financing mechanisms and barriers to public-private partnerships (PPP)**. One notable barrier is difficulties in public procurement processes e.g. Johannesburg reported that during implementation of an energy efficiency project they put out tendering for private actors but were unable to contract due to inflexibility of the municipality: city officials reported that the municipality cannot contract a third party, who may want to do off-balance sheet funding (C40 Cities, 2016). Private actors are also disincentivised to apply for public procurement and invest resources if the chances of success of winning the contract is low or see high barriers to apply for tendering (e.g. red tape, overly complex process).

Further barriers posed by regulation are **insufficient clarity from government** on climate change legislation, **lack of vertical alignment** between national and subnational governments and uncertainty over regulatory and tax policies. Cities have a **lack of control over policies** and enabling environment conditions that can encourage private investment. Another source of barrier is posed by the mismatch of the scope of infrastructure or large investment projects with the administrative boundaries of cities.

Planning and information barriers

Quantifying costs, benefits and co-benefits poses a significant barrier caused by lack of capacities, technical expertise or lack of data. Demonstrating the viability of climate-related projects is crucial in increasing their uptake and ensuring public acceptance, which is key to long-term strategy implementation. At the same time, assessing the costs and benefits of climate action is a fundamental part of climate policy and decision-making. Economic appraisal can inform decision-making for improving allocative efficiency, i.e. do the benefits of a project outweigh its costs? If so, the project is judged to be allocative efficient, i.e. investing in the project contributes to higher economic efficiency (European Investment Advisory Hub, 2022). Among other aspects, revealing socio-economic benefits of climate investment projects is an important indicator of the investment's effectiveness, and hence provides relevant information to attract climate finance. Besides understanding costs and benefits, municipalities also need to communicate the value of their climate-related projects (i.e. the benefit, co-benefit) to attain buy-in from citizens, investors, and policymakers. **Effective communication and engagement campaigns** are crucial to educate citizens, potential investors and policymakers about the value of these projects.

Difficulty in integrating climate goals into other interventions and infrastructure planning often means that climate-related projects are given lower priority than initiatives that address other needs, such as investments in education, healthcare, and public safety. **Short-term thinking** of decisions-makers also contributes to this problem through favouring short-term rewards over long-term benefits, tendency toward short-term return over longer-term interests, being reactive rather than proactive (Spurling, 2020). Another issue that further complicates climate related investment is the inherent **conflict between long-term development and budget-cycles**.

The development of climate projects also needs to be **aligned with local strategies**, workplans to ensure they address specific needs. This alignment helps contribute to broader socio-economic goals, such as job creation, public health, and infrastructure development, thereby achieving co-benefits that are meaningful to the local community.

Institutional and organisation barriers

Limited capacity and lack of expertise to prepare **investor ready and "bankable" project proposals** for public or private investment, may be more prevalent in smaller municipalities with limited staff and experience. **Project concepts** and ideas exist in many cities, but they are often **not well-structured or designed** in terms of bankability. Lack of investor-ready bankable projects of sufficient size and quality is one of the major roadblocks to scaling up urban finance. Better coordination of existing resources could help, together with improving the municipality's capacity to manage the project development process through to investment decision and implementation. Climate related projects frequently require technical, feasibility, and impact studies, which cities may not afford because public budgets are tight, and they have limited direct access to external project preparation finance and support (Carter & Boukerche, 2020). Barriers could be overcome by national, regional, EU-level and multilateral support to build capacities and provide project preparatory finance.

Lack of available funding could be caused by the **mismatch between local needs and funding available** from European and national programmes, differences in political priorities between national governments and city administrations and **reduced government transfers**, state subsidies due to austerity measures and slow growth.

European governments are facing competition in allocating **scarce public budgets** between the digital transition, military expenditures and investment in social infrastructure. They must also balance high

inflation and interest rates with higher costs in public debt management, and the cost of an ageing population. The political will to invest in the green transition may fall short considering these competing factors (European Environment Agency, 2023). At a municipal level several cities face with **budget capacity constraints** and fiscal sustainability. National and subnational budgets have been heavily impacted by the economic effects and impact of municipal revenues of the COVID-19 pandemic, the energy crisis and Russia's invasion of Ukraine, which led to increased expenses and in turn higher funding needs.

A closer look at EU Mission city needs and barriers to finance

The study "Funding and Financing the Zero Emissions Journey: Urban Visions from the 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission" published in 2023 outlines the financial readiness, proactiveness, barriers, and needs of European cities striving for climate neutrality (Ulpiani et al., 2023). The study uses data collected through the EU Mission to investigate how cities are fostering climate investment. The EU Mission's large-scale dataset from 362 cities that provided self-assessments through the Expression of Interest questionnaire analysis gives further insight into cities' needs and barriers to finance.

Most respondent cities, according to the study, have not yet estimated the total investment needed for climate neutrality. Among those that have, estimates range widely, with a median of approximately 1 billion euros per city, some cities estimate needs as high as 1.2 trillion euros.

European cities face several barriers in financing climate action, including:

- Lack of funding/financing schemes: this is the top barrier, cited by 66% of cities.
- Prohibitive investment costs: high initial capital costs are a significant hurdle, particularly in the energy and transport sectors.
- Slow/disaggregated financial processes: many cities struggle with slow and fragmented financial processes.
- Difficulties in building public-private collaborations: establishing effective collaborations between public and private sectors is challenging for many cities.
- Insufficient administrative and operational capacities: a lack of capacity to create bankable projects and manage fiscal and financial planning is a major issue. Cities lack the necessary administrative and technical knowledge and highlighted their low preparedness in dealing with funding.
- Regulatory and budgetary challenges: cities face regulatory restrictions, fiscal constraints, and the impact of COVID-19 on local government revenues.
- Fragmentation of responsibilities: the institutional setup often leads to fragmented responsibilities, making it difficult to attract investment. Fragmented responsibilities, insufficient administrative capacity, and regulatory red tape also hinder financial mobilization.

Cities express a **strong need for capacity building** in areas such as knowledge of climate finance, investment planning, and project development to become finance ready. In terms of funding, cities are looking to various funding sources, including regional, national, and EU funds, private financing, and their own funds, but heavy reliance on traditional sources of finance was observed by the authors of the study. Looking at the estimations provided by cities:

- Public funds: regional, national, and EU funds are commonly included in cities' financial plans, with varying degrees of reliance, highlighting that to differing levels they rely on higher levels of public funding.

- Private financing: there is minimal engagement of private sources, only 68 cities included private financing, with most indicating it would cover no more than 40% of total costs.
- Own funds: 74 cities plan to use their own funds, but this typically covers a small share ($\leq 20\%$) of the total investment needed.
- The use of innovative financing instruments is limited, with Energy Performance Contracting being the most popular. Most cities (77.1%) declared no experience with innovative financing instruments, although 169 cities expressed their intention to explore potential avenues. Cities expressed the need for innovative financing models and approaches, such as crowdfunding, tax incentives, leasing contracts, loans for energy retrofits, and PPP.

Since the UP2030 project also contributes to the EU Mission's goals, GGGI has initiated collaboration with the other EU Mission partner project, NetZeroCities (NZC)¹. In this context, GGGI started collaborating with Bankers without Boundaries (BwB), the responsible partner in NZC for assisting cities with their investment planning and financing.

During GGGI's engagement with a BwB from the NZC project in M14, GGGI discussed the progress and challenges faced by the participating cities. As of GGGI's engagement in M14, ten cities have already prepared and finalized their EU Mission Cities Investment Plans², which have been approved by the European Commission, obtaining the EU Mission Label. In M15, 23 additional cities were awarded the EU Mission Label (European Commission, 2024). The remaining cities involved in the EU Mission are still in the process of developing their Investment Plans. Out of the 10 UP2030 pilot cities, eight are also EU Cities Mission Cities: Budapest, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki and Zagreb. According to the discussions, the main findings of BwB with the cities is that from the first 10 cities, none could achieve 80% carbon neutrality solely through public funding. During the discussions with BwB several **barriers and needs** were identified:

- Practical implementation of financial instruments,
- Effective communication between city departments,
- Financial assistance needed by cities,
- Difficulty in estimating financial costs,
- Guidance on making financial assumptions,
- Importance of case studies and peer-to-peer learning,
- The utility of seeing how financial solutions are implemented in other cities,
- Challenges in maintaining and updating contact databases post-project.

Both the findings of the "Funding and Financing the Zero Emissions Journey NZC" study and GGGI's engagements with NZC partners reinforce the observations from the literature review. Both the literature and EU Mission cities identify limited budget capacities, difficulties in accessing finance, and the challenges of engaging private investors as significant barriers to financing climate actions. These findings emphasise

¹ Project website: <https://netzerocities.eu/>

² The EU Mission Cities Investment Plan, as part of the Climate City Contracts (CCC), is a strategic framework designed to help cities achieve their climate neutrality goals. The plan focuses on identifying and mobilising the necessary financial resources to support the implementation of climate action projects.

the need to support European cities in utilising innovative financial solutions, increasing their administrative and technical capacities, and with engaging the private sector.

3.2 UP2030 pilot city needs

Innovative, participatory and inclusive engagement activities with cities aimed to identify needs for updating and barriers cities face. It therefore constitutes the basis for the whole 5UP process, guiding the co-design of the visions and transformation visions and pathways and form the baseline evaluation in terms of planning and design related financing schemes, along with policy and governance arrangements (feeding to WP5 and T5.3). During the project, three city engagements activities were conducted by the consortium and GGGI with the aim to understand the barriers and challenges pilot cities face and validate literature findings:

1. Workshops on needs and barriers identification: conducted by WP2 partners with the support of cities' local liaison partners (under T2.3 "City and stakeholder engagement for the identification of needs for upgrading, barriers and drivers of change"), to identify cities' needs, barriers, and opportunities for urban climate interventions. (M3-M6)
2. Survey on financing needs and barriers: conducted by GGGI (in WP5 under T5.3), building on the results of the Workshops on needs identification, the project team sent out a survey to pilot cities in order to gather detailed insights on how cities finance their climate initiatives, budgetary and fiscal stability, the challenges faced, and strategies employed to assess costs and benefits and mobilise finance and funding. (M11)
3. Focused workshops on financing, CBA and the guides: conducted by GGGI (in WP5 under T5.3), they were held to gain a deeper understanding of cities' financing barriers, needs and preferences for guide functionalities, along with cities' needs in relation to estimating costs and benefits. The workshop also provided valuable insights for the development of the Guides. (M15)

Figure 3: The structure of pilot city engagements and their contribution to the guides

3.2.1 Workshops on identification of needs and barriers (WP2)

The UP2030 Planning cycle (Rocco et al., 2024) has been developed by TUD (Delft University of Technology) to guide cities in their planning practices, aligned with the 5UP framework and the project timeline. As part of the cycle the first steps were to identify cities' "needs" to unlock the transformations and pave the way for co-visioning, implementation and upscaling of urban climate interventions.

Figure 4: The TUD/UP2030 planning cycle

Guided under WP2 (T2.3) UP2030 cities have conducted workshops (M3-M6) on identification of gaps, needs, and barriers, working closely with their Liaisons, and their key stakeholders to understand **what the barriers to change were and what was needed to overcome them** in their UP2030 neighbourhood demonstration projects. Taking the learnings from deliverable D2.2 and D2.3 UP2030 benchmarking report against state-of-the-art and identification of pilot opportunities, cities identified the needs, barriers, and opportunities on five recurring governance dimensions that emerged from the literature:

- Co-developing and monitoring
- Creative and flourishing
- Systemic & decentralised approach
- Capacity & community Building
- **Sustainable funding**

This section summarises UP2030 cities' barriers, needs, and gaps identified in the workshop under the dimension of sustainable funding.

As per the results of the workshop, the project team found that UP2030 pilot cities have specific financial needs and face a variety of barriers in their efforts to implement their UP2030 neighbourhood demonstration projects.

- In Belfast, the primary needs are subsidies and concessions to support a just transition, while the main barriers include high costs and a lack of funding for retrofits and maintenance of greening.
- Budapest needs comprehensive business plans, expert planning services, alternative financial sources, community funding, SME involvement, CBA, and improved coordination through a high-level coordinative body. The barriers in Budapest centre around a lack of coordination and communication within projects and the organisation.
- Granollers requires funds from energy companies, infrastructure for renewable energy, public investment in affordable housing, subsidies for vulnerable populations, and support from European funds. The barriers here include high costs for public transport and energy investments, regulatory frameworks that lack agility, unpredictability of external factors, and a need for public investment to balance housing costs and returns.
- In Istanbul, there is a need for financial incentives and innovative financial models to lower initial investment costs for renewable energy, with barriers including high initial costs, lack of readily available financing options, and concerns about return on investment.
- Lisbon identified a need to incentivise and change the current funding system, enhancing investment capacity among citizens and companies, and developing inclusive financing mechanisms. The barriers include financing that requires upfront investment with delayed incentives, and a lack of ideas on generating sustainable finance.
- Milan needs resources for urban regeneration projects, potential involvement of the private sector in green area maintenance through incentives and calculating the economic value of ecosystem services. The barriers in Milan include insufficient economic resources for climate neutrality interventions, inadequate maintenance resources, and public-private agreements that cover implementation but not maintenance costs.
- Muenster did not address specific needs but mentioned costs in general as a barrier.
- Rotterdam needs integrated financial streams, collaboration with housing corporations, alignment of public support with governmental goals, and standardised integrated budgeting practices. The barriers are institutional resistance to integrated approaches, lack of financial resources for stakeholders, and time pressures from scheduled projects.
- Thessaloniki needs funding for public space restoration, highlighting natural-based elements, financial incentives for renovations, and securing funding for proposed solutions. The barriers include a lack of clear financial mechanisms.
- Lastly, Zagreb at city level needs to launch new financial mechanisms for energy efficiency and renewable energy projects but did not address specific barriers in relation to the city pilot project.

Overall, the most common barriers that occurred across many cities include high costs, lack of funding and regulatory and policy barriers for implementing and maintaining climate interventions. Another prevalent theme challenges with coordination among departments and integrated approaches. Addressing these

issues through innovative financial models, PPP, and improved regulatory frameworks is crucial for the success of urban climate interventions. By establishing high-level coordinative bodies or platform and the adoption of standardised integrated budgeting practices that align financial resources with overarching climate action goals. This facilitates a cohesive and unified approach to project funding and implementation to maximise the impacts of the climate action projects.

3.2.2 Survey on financing needs and barriers (WP5)

In M11, GGGI has sent out a written survey to the ten pilot cities of the project: Belfast, Budapest, Granollers, Istanbul, Lisbon, Milan, Muenster, Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, and Zagreb.

The survey's objectives were to gather insights on how cities finance their climate initiatives, the challenges they face, and the strategies they employ to overcome these obstacles.

The main categories of the questions were:

- Budget and financial capacity: assessing the city's budget capacity and specific budget lines for climate action.
- Financial challenges and barriers: identifying financial obstacles and regulatory barriers to implementing climate action plans.
- Funding sources: determining primary and potential funding sources, including EU funding programmes and other financing mechanisms.
- Cost estimation: understanding methodologies and tools used for estimating the costs of climate actions and sustainability projects.
- Co-benefit estimation: evaluating methods to estimate environmental, social, and economic co-benefits of climate actions.
- Revenue-generating projects: identifying business cases where climate projects generate income for the city.

The survey questions sent out to cities can be found in Appendix 1: Financing capacities and needs questionnaire sent to pilot cities.

In order to support cities' survey responses with data and fully understand their financial capacities, sources of funds and level of debt, GGGI has also asked pilot cities to provide detailed data on their municipality budget (historic and forecasted expenses and incomes for the past five and next five years). Moreover, to assess pilot cities' cost and benefits calculation, and financial planning procedures, GGGI has requested cities to share any assessments and calculations they have on their demonstration project's costs and benefits.

Out of 10 UP2030 cities, four filled in the survey. Those cities that did not fill out the survey cited two main barriers that prevented them from it

- a. Budgetary and financial information is spread across different city departments (internally) and organisations (externally), and knowledge exchange between the different departments, organisations and UP2030 municipality members is resource intensive or not sufficient. As an example, in the case of Belfast, it is not a unitary authority, budgetary and financial information is spread across several organisations and not necessarily easy to isolate for just Belfast city. For

example, several central government departments would be working towards the climate agenda but on a regional bases (Northern Ireland) as opposed to city level.

- b. Out of the 10 pilot cities, eight are also EU Cities Mission Cities. When the survey was sent out, three pilot cities (Muenster, Rotterdam, and Istanbul) were in the process of preparing their 2030 Climate Neutrality Investment Plans within the framework of the EU Mission's NZC project. Cities noted that due to the preparation of the Investment Plan (IP) has already put significant resource needs on cities and their respective departments, hence had insufficient capacities to provide information. These cities have also asked GGGI to extract relevant information from the finalised Investment Plans.

Main takeaways from the survey responses

All four cities — Budapest, Granollers, Lisbon, and Milan — have their debt ratio centrally regulated, and the level of debt is below the centrally defined limit. For instance, to meet their temporary cash flow needs, local authorities in Spain, including Granollers, may arrange short-term credit financing, not exceeding one year, provided that the total amount does not exceed 30% of their operating income of the previous year (Ministerio de Hacienda, 2004). Milan, as every municipality in Italy, can take out new loans and has access to other forms of debt financing available on the market only if the total amount of yearly interest does not exceed 10% of the revenues from two years prior to taking out the loan (Ministero dell'Interno, 2023). Three out of the four cities were given access to credit by the government in the past five years, Budapest has indicated in the survey that it has not been able to get access from the central government and decisions regarding capital expenditures and financing through loans are solely based on central directives in the country.

As per their responses on the survey, all four cities specific budget lines dedicated to sustainable urban development and climate action. However, this could not be cross-checked as the publicly available and provided budgetary data is too high level, making it difficult to verify the exact allocations and their effectiveness. Three of the cities have budget for contingencies related to negative climate induced disasters. Only two pilot cities provided GGGI with supporting budgetary data, however the data provided was too high-level to allow for a detailed analysis and to draw specific conclusions relevant to GGGI's queries.

The four cities prioritise large investment projects using a combination of strategic plans, technical recommendations, financial tools, and predefined priority levels. Budapest relies on municipal assembly-approved strategic plans, while Granollers uses a methodology aligned with its Municipal Action Program. Lisbon employs finance and accounting tools like SAP and analytical accounting, and Milan follows a Three-Year Plan of Public Works to define and prioritise projects.

The four cities—Budapest, Granollers, Lisbon, and Milan—rely on a variety of funding sources to support their climate action plans. Common sources include city taxation, user charges and fees, central government grants and subsidies, other grants, and various loan types. Additionally, these cities utilise specific funding mechanisms such as land and infrastructure leases, land sales, PPP, and Special Purpose Vehicles (SPVs). Some also engage in debt refinancing instruments and collaborate with Energy Service Companies (ESCO) for energy efficiency projects. This diversified funding approach helps them address the financial challenges and barriers they face in implementing their climate initiatives. To finance large investments the main sources of funding include a mix of own revenues, development loans, government grants, EU funds, credits and bank loans, Next Generation Funds, and co-financing. Additionally, in some cities, projects are supported by private investments and contributions from institutional investors and private operators specialising in real estate and infrastructure development. Reliance on EU funding

programmes is prominent in all UP2030 pilot cities, programmes cities have utilised include Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, LIFE, Erasmus+ and ESF+.

Generally, the four cities employ a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods, internal studies, and external data sources, e.g., national statistics, or more specifically Granollers relies on CDP (the Carbon Disclosure Project) to estimate the costs associated with their climate action plans and sustainability projects. Lisbon is currently developing a methodology that includes estimating resources needed to achieve climate objectives, listing cost items, estimating benefits, and return on investment. In relation to the quantified cost and benefits of cities' pilots none of the 10 cities could provide GGGI with a calculation. Cities utilise a mix of indicators (e.g. energy savings indicators from SECAP), models, and assessment tools, such as the Ecosystem Service Assessment tool (software InVEST) to measure different environmental, social and economic co-benefits of their climate actions. The main reason for that was that at the time of the survey, pilots were still in an early phase of development (e.g. Milan at the time had not yet selected their pilot's location) to estimate costs and benefits. GGGI has also seen an example of projects that generate income (or save costs). In Granollers, a public energy company has been created for two district heating networks fuelled by biomass and the city has also installed a photovoltaic solar plant and electric vehicle (EV) charge points in public spaces.

The main financial challenges and barriers to implementing climate action plans in the four cities include revenue constraints due to COVID-19 and inflation, minimal growth in state subsidies (prominent in Hungary), and rising energy costs. There are difficulties in establishing specific municipal programs, restrictive short-term investment criteria (e.g., in Granollers if an investment does not generate income, it is no longer an investment criterion), and challenges in human resources and PPP. Governance issues, regulatory barriers, and misalignment with external funding further complicate efforts. Regulatory and administrative restrictions make it difficult to take out municipal loans, to approve multi-year projects, and to implement innovative financing. Additionally, the unpredictability of extreme weather events restricts investment, and there is a need to integrate climate actions into existing municipal interventions efficiently. An important challenge highlighted was the quantification of costs to climate adaptation actions.

Solutions suggested by cities to overcome barriers include becoming self-sufficient in financing, decentralising decision-making, quantifying social and environmental co-benefits for budget inclusion, quantifying adaptation costs for better planning, shifting to long-term investment visions, implementing green policies and taxation, accessing innovative financing mechanisms, and integrating climate actions into other municipal interventions for efficient resource allocation.

3.2.3 [Focused workshops on financing, CBA and guide development \(WP5\)](#)

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the cities' general needs and challenges in financing and CBA, alongside their preferences for guide functionalities, three workshops were organised. These workshops targeted UP2030 city officials and were done online with pilot cities during M15.

Table 1: Workshop participants and votes

	Participating pilot cities	Total individual participants from pilot cities*
Workshop 1 06/03	Lisbon, Belfast and Muenster	7
Workshop 2 07/03	Rotterdam, Istanbul, Milan, Thessaloniki	4
Workshop 3 12/03	Budapest, Granollers, Zagreb	7
	10 cities	18

*Number of participants varied across questions

The goal of the workshop was to understand **cities financing and CBA related needs** and gauge what guide functionalities they need the most and would use to help them obtain finance. The project team used Mentimeter³ to poll in real time the participating cities. The aggregated results of the poll helped GGGI shed light on what functionalities cities are looking for and areas to focus on when preparing the financial and CBA guides. In each workshop, all answers were ranked by participants. The ranking system works such that an item ranked first receives points equal to the total number of items in that question, the item ranked second receives one point less, and so on. When aggregating the results across all workshops, GGGI summed these points to determine the total rank for each answer.

The first question (Figure 5) delved into the primary obstacles cities encounter when seeking funding. As per responses received, it was clear that lack of funds poses the largest obstacle to cities in implementing climate initiatives. Furthermore, the second highest ranked answer highlights the importance of estimating costs and benefits for budget planning and obtaining finance.

³ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

Figure 5: The primary obstacles cities encounter when seeking funding for climate initiatives

Cities often struggle due to the absence of a dedicated budget for climate action, requiring departments aiming to implement climate action to compete for funds with other municipal projects and departments. Centralised budgeting results in misaligned departmental objectives and budgets shaped by political will. Additionally, poor communication between departments, particularly between finance and project leads in climate or urban planning, exacerbates these issues. Individuals involved in projects are frequently not directly connected to finance, making information flow difficult. Furthermore, the finance department often does not participate in these projects, adding to the complexity. Cities also highlighted that estimating non-tangible benefits presents a significant challenge, lowering the attractiveness of a project to obtain finance.

During the workshop, UP2030 pilot cities indicated the highest preference for a database on financial instruments (Figure 6). During literature review the project team has found there are several databases and knowledge repositories on financial instruments and mechanisms are available for cities (e.g., NZC Finance Guidance Tool, Cities Climate Finance Leadership Alliance's (CCFLA) Financial Instruments Toolkit for more on similar tools available see section 4.2.1). This need might indicate either a lack of awareness of existing solutions, or that there is a lack of time and resources to use them. When comparing the answers to questions 1 and 2, it can be seen that the ranking of desired functionalities is not fully aligned with the ranking of the needs identified (e.g., limited information on sources available was ranked 7th in Q1).

Figure 6: The functionality cities would find most useful in a green finance guide

Some cities indicated that they have a dedicated financial advisor and, or a team focusing on obtaining international and EU funding (e.g., Rotterdam). During the workshop, cities have also expressed the importance of social awareness to create pressure on government through citizens' expectations and the need for existing business cases and success stories that help obtain finance.

Participants highlighted that cities generally lack comprehensive information about different sources of finance and funding. Decision-makers and policy-makers often do not possess in-depth knowledge of these financial sources. This knowledge gap results in a preference for traditional instruments and scepticism towards novel ones due to the absence of information and political will. Additionally, rigid budgeting processes and local contexts render some financial instruments unfeasible. Cities emphasise that budgeting and treasury department officials need the most information on financial instruments and funding sources (Figure 7). The reason behind this, is because these officials play a central role in financial planning and decision-making. Their knowledge is crucial for integrating financial strategies across departments, facilitating effective communication, and ensuring long-term financial sustainability. Effective communication between financial departments and project implementation teams is crucial. Well-informed budgeting officials can better identify and secure diverse funding opportunities, supporting the successful implementation of city projects. Projects often require funding from multiple sources, including grants, loans, and PPP. Budgeting and treasury officials are in a position to integrate this financial knowledge across various departments, ensuring that projects are adequately funded, and financial risks are managed.

Figure 7: Who would need the most financial guidance in the municipality

The workshop reinforced literature findings, highlighting that cities are seeking assistance in evaluating costs and benefits to secure financing for climate action. Focusing on benefits, cities ranked health benefits the highest, followed by environmental quality benefits they need the most help on (Figure 8). The complexity of benefits and costs associated with climate projects makes it difficult to quantify and evaluate non-tangible benefits like improved public health and ecosystem services. This requires sophisticated analytical techniques and specialised expertise that many cities lack.

Figure 8: Important benefits and co-benefits to be considered in a CBA

Conducting detailed and accurate CBAs requires specialised expertise in environmental economics, advanced modelling techniques, and the ability to integrate complex data sets. Many cities lack the in-house expertise needed to perform these sophisticated analyses. One of the main challenges is accurately quantifying non-tangible benefits such as improved public health, enhanced ecosystem services, and social equity. These benefits are often difficult to measure and require advanced methodologies and valuation techniques. Moreover, different departments within cities often approach evaluation differently, leading to inconsistent assessments that do not always consider the full range of aspects outside their specific scopes. An example from Budapest illustrates this challenge: the municipality's climate department

proposed the installation of artificial shades in areas where nature-based solutions were not feasible. However, this proposal conflicted with the design guidelines of the urban planning and design department, stalling the process, prioritising the city's aesthetic and ecological standards over immediate climate interventions to manage urban heat stress. This situation underscores how different departments evaluate proposals through their specific lenses and objectives, often leading to conflicts and a lack of holistic consideration of all potential benefits and trade-offs. Additionally, cities highlighted that "benefits" of urban projects may not be recognised as "benefits" by citizens, especially when they are spread over time or across different locations, adding another layer of complexity to the evaluation process

Figure 9: Main challenges in conducting cost and benefit assessment for climate projects

Moreover, data challenges are significant. Cities often lack robust reporting mechanisms and comprehensive data at the necessary scales and locations. This lack of consistent and high-quality data complicates the process of conducting reliable cost-benefit analysis. Cities have been consistent, and their responses reflected that they most need technical guidance on cost and benefit assessment (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Most preferred option on the kind of support cities need in relation to CBA

Main takeaways from engagements with UP2030 pilot cities

Key barriers faced by the pilot cities reinforced main findings from the literature review:

1. **High costs and lack of funding** for implementing and maintaining climate interventions.
2. **Lack of coordination and communication** within city departments and external stakeholders (financers) and challenges in aligning departmental objectives with planning and budgeting.
3. **Regulatory and policy barriers:** regulatory frameworks lack agility and flexibility, regulatory limit on debt, and there is misalignment with existing funding opportunities and local needs.

4. **Data and technical challenges** in assessing costs and benefits of climate interventions.

Key needs identified by the pilot cities respond to barriers pilot cities face and also reinforce findings from the literature review on city needs:

1. Understanding different **sources of finance**, diversifying sources of finance and funding, and utilising innovative financing instruments and models.
2. High-level coordinative bodies to **enhance coordination and communication** within municipalities to develop financial plans and bankable projects.
3. **Capacity building and resources** to build technical capacity for carrying out cost-benefit analysis.

4 Green finance

4.1 Introduction to green finance

Green finance refers to investment (such as equity, bonds, or loans) or fiscal measures (such as tax breaks or subsidies) that aim to either mitigate ecologically harmful energy generation, increase its ecological sustainability, or enable its adaptation to climate change (Babic, 2024). For example, energy projects and activities aimed at mitigation and adaptation are being financially supported and enabled through either direct financing or fiscal measures that forego potential tax revenues.

The figure below shows what constitutes a green "project" in order to understand the definition of green finance:

Figure 11: Diagram for understanding green finance, source: (C40 Cities, 2022)

Since 2017, green finance activity in Europe has increased fivefold. European capital markets raised more than €750bn in green finance from 2017 to 2021 across bond, equity, and loan markets (Breen, 2022). Moreover, in the forthcoming years, the green finance market is poised for further growth, fuelled by the increasing popularity of investment strategies centred around environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations (Salas Compás, 2023). As cities aim to avoid the most severe impacts of climate change through intelligent urban transformation, their governments are ramping up their climate commitments. They are also working to mobilise additional private capital by creating innovative financial instruments that serve a catalytic role and ensuring the effectiveness and impact of their green finance.

While green finance in Europe is growing fast, it is still not enough to meet the required levels of investment for Europe to fulfil its net zero commitments (Breen, 2022). Despite cities' green finance momentum, local governments continue to face significant barriers in mobilising green finance, as explored in section 3 of this report. European cities' barriers to scale-up green finance, identified through GGGI's engagement with pilot cities (refer to section 3.2), literature review (section 3.1) and engagement with other tool providers on urban finance (detailed in the following section, 4.2.1), and which will be addressed by the Green Finance Guide, can be grouped into three areas:

1. **Heavy reliance on traditional financial instruments** due to limited understanding or awareness of the applicability of innovative financing instruments and strategies - by themselves or in conjunction with conventional financial instruments – for green projects.

2. **Constrained administrative capacity and proactiveness** to (i) identify and promote financially viable green projects and (ii) develop a bankable and investor-ready pipeline of green projects in coordination with environmental, financial, and city planning departments, and (iii) difficulties in building public-private collaborations, and (iv) difficulties in engaging with private sector finance stakeholders.
3. **Limited regulation and institutional arrangements** to leverage private finance (i), e.g., share of co-financing from cities, fiscal restrictions, impossibility to increase debt, and (ii) slow and fragmented financial processes, and lack of collaboration between city departments.

The degree of these barriers changes based on the city's profile. For example, incumbent cities with experience issuing green bonds have fewer administrative capacity barriers and a lower reliance on traditional instruments. Moreover, they have an understanding of mobilising finance and implementing financial agreements for high capital-intensive urban infrastructure projects, such as transportation systems and local electricity production investments. The Green Finance Guide aims to support "inexperienced" cities in green finance mobilisation. European cities are characterised by facing significant hurdles in mobilising green finance and require technical assistance to develop the capacity and knowledge necessary to overcome them.

4.2 [Green Finance Guide](#)

To help cities address the barriers to scaling up green finance, supporting the financing of green projects and the funding for its operations, maintenance and refinancing, the Green Finance Guide will provide:

- an overview of the existing green funding and finance instruments and mechanisms for different economic sectors, and project's readiness and risks levels linked with case examples,
- an explanation of how the existing green finance instruments can complement each other and work with economic instruments to form financial strategies that can leverage private finance with case examples of their utilisation,
- an overview of finance and technical assistance providers for cities to support the project's identification and development up to bankability.

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, the Guide will provide the solutions stated on Table 2.

Table 2: Barriers, needs and solutions to scale up green finance in cities

Barriers and needs identified	Green Finance Guide solution to overcome barrier
<p>1. Heavy reliance on traditional financial instruments, due to low understanding or awareness of the applicability of innovative financing instruments and strategies - by themselves or in conjunction with conventional financial instruments – for green projects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cities rely heavily on 'conventional' instruments such as public financing and EU funding. Despite their willingness to exploit innovative financing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase funding sources, financial and economic instruments and mechanisms, classified as conventional and innovative, with case studies exemplifying their standalone success application. • Showcase innovative green finance, classified as (i) innovation

<p>instruments and mechanisms cities lack experience in their utilisation (Ulpiani et al., 2023)(to see UP2030 city responses through needs assessment workshops and survey, see section 3.2).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cities aim to utilise integrated financial solutions, mixing conventional with innovative green finance to improve creditworthiness, transparency, and fiscal management. • Cities aim to gain an understanding of the adequate use of funding, financial instruments and mechanisms in combination with economic instruments and the interaction between multiple financial products and different investor audiences to finance multiple sectors with small—to large projects. 	<p>in financial arrangements where both conventional and innovative financial instruments and mechanisms are used in conjunction with economic instruments to leverage private finance and (ii) innovation in engaging with the private sector.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show case examples linked to instruments providing examples to municipalities on the application and blending various financial instruments and mechanisms.
<p>2. Constrained administrative capacity and proactiveness to (i) identify and promote financially viable green projects, (ii) to develop investor-ready pipeline of green projects in coordination with environmental, financial and city planning departments, (iii) difficulties in building collaborations between public and private sectors, and (iv) difficulties in engaging with private sector finance stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A 2023 study using data collected through the EU Mission on 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities shows that 63% of the European cities surveyed do not work with established investment/finance partners to build an investor-ready pipeline of green projects and prefer to focus on the development of their climate action plans. This shows that cities require investment preparedness assistance, before aiming at accessing financing (Ulpiani et al., 2023)and refer to section 3.1). • 'Knowledge of climate finance' (181 eligible cities, 50%), (ii) 'Investment planning' (157 cities, 43.4%), and (iii) 'Project development through pre-feasibility to finance-ready' (150 cities, 41.4%) (Ulpiani et al., 2023). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List stakeholders providing technical assistance for cities for the development of financial readiness as well as the ideation of bankable projects. • List of private sector stakeholder types, with a few explicitly named, that can support the financing of urban projects, such as commercial banks
<p>3. Limited regulation and institutional arrangements to leverage private finance (i) e.g., share of co-</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Showcase economic and financial instruments and mechanisms that

<p><i>financing from cities, fiscal restrictions, impossibility to increase debt, (ii) slow and fragmented financial processes, lack of collaboration between city departments.</i></p>	<p>can be filtered according to municipality context and needs. i.e., financial instruments and mechanisms classified per relationship of project readiness and risk, or filtering out debt instruments from green finance options.</p>
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4.2.1 Existing guides and tools

There are numerous platforms, databases, and tools designed to support cities in financing green investments. These resources offer essential services such as financial instrument access, investor connections, and technical assistance. Figure 12 highlights some of the most significant resources but it is not exhaustive.

Figure 12: Existing tools to support green finance mobilisation of cities

After a thorough examination, GGGI identified the following sources as the most useful and relevant for cities on financial instruments and funding sources:

- The NZC Finance Guidance Tool provides an overview of instruments after filling in a short a questionnaire, which suggests the most suitable financial instrument(s) based on users' responses to a pre-defined list of questions with yes-no answers (NetZeroCities, n.d.). The Tool's purpose is to support cities in the development of the Investment Plans (as part of Climate City Contract to attain the EU Mission label). The Tool has been recently updated focusing on refining filtering

questions, clearing redundancies, and enhancing background functionalities and the user interface. Available at: <https://netzerocities.app/financeGuidanceTool>.

- The CCFLA Financial Instruments Toolkit is an extensive library of 72 identified financial instruments across several different financial categories which users can explore using a range of filters to find the instrument that best suits their needs, mainly targeting developing regions (Cities Climate Finance Leadership Alliance, n.d.). The Toolkit's library will be updated by the end of 2024. Available at: <https://citiesclimatefinance.org/financial-instruments#instruments-library>.
- The Innovative Financial Instruments for Climate Adaptation initially developed by the International Institute for Sustainable Development, updated in 2024 by the NAP Global Network, presents a list of instruments for countries in the global south to utilize in adapting to climate change (National Adaptation Plan (NAP) Global Network and International Institute for Sustainable Development, 2024). Available at: <https://napglobalnetwork.org/innovative-financing/>.
- The Covenant of Mayors - Europe's Financing Opportunities provides an EU-focused look into available EU funding programs, instruments from financial institutions and alternative financial institutions alongside available technical and advisory services (European Commission, 2024). Available at: https://eu-mayors.ec.europa.eu/en/resources/funding_guide.

During the project, GGGI has engaged with both (i) NCZ's partner, the Frankfurt School of Finance and Management (FS), and (ii) Climate Policy Institute (CPI), a member of CCFLA, both responsible for the development of the NZC and CCFLA tools respectively.

In relation to NZC Finance Guidance Tool from FS, GGGI learned of the issues the tool could not address: i) checklists to support instrument use, ii) addressing private financing challenges (especially for public goods), and iii) regulatory challenges in carbon markets, continuous content updates, videos of city case studies (implementation difficulties) and linking instruments to cities' regulatory background.

FS also shared insights with GGGI on challenges identified through their engagement with NZC cities:

- Cities need help in making accurate project cost estimations.
- Financial institutions do not recognise cities as a distinct client group.
- There is a lack of incentives for private finance players to invest in municipalities' climate projects.

On the use of the tool FS informed GGGI that cities have shown limited engagement with case studies or detailed tabs and that climate teams are not the primary users of the tool.

CPI observed that cities have shown limited engagement with the tool so far; potential reasons could be that cities are not aware of the Toolkit or do not have the necessary capacities and time to engage with it.

All these tools and engagement with the two tool providers (FS and CPI), with UP2030 partners and cities (refer to section 3.2) have provided inspiration and valuable insights and inputs for the development of UP2030's Green Finance Guide.

Table 3: Identifying the value added of the new Green Finance Guide

Gaps to be addressed by the Green Finance Guide	Similarities between existing prominent tools and the Green Finance Guide	Differences that add value to the Green Finance Guide
<p>Informing climate and finance teams within the city's government on green finance solutions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide detailed information on financing instruments – such as definition, benefits and challenges for its utilisation - which may be discouraging for climate experts with limited financial knowledge • Provide case examples linked to financial instruments and mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Green Finance Guide allows the location of case examples based on sector and climate impact • The Green Finance Guide shows case examples that highlight the reason why a certain green project is considered bankable • The Green Finance Guide is embedded in the UP2030 Service Platform (T5.2) to provide a "one-stop-shop" solution for cities that wish to implement and upscale their climate interventions • The Green Finance Guide links instruments with EU Taxonomy categories of investment
<p>Linking financial instruments to cities' regulatory background</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not addressed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Green Finance Guide provides case examples where financial instruments are used in conjunction with cities' economic incentives • Cities can filter different types of instruments (debt, equity and public finance – domestic and international). Cities can easily filter out debt finance when there is a regulatory limit, i.e. cities are not permitted to take on debt.
<p>Addressing private financing challenges (especially for public goods)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic instruments explorer (web-based), which allows filtering financial instruments based on the economic sector, funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Green Finance Guide shows relevant private sector financiers, showcased within

	sources, and instrument type.	<p>the risk-readiness spectrum of different types of projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Green Finance Guide lists stakeholders that provide technical assistance for green finance mobilisation.
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To address barriers, needs, and gaps identified, GGGI developed three interlinked modules in the Green Finance Guide in which users can search and filter for green finance solutions, relevant stakeholders and case examples to arrive at a short-list of solutions:

1. Financial instruments and mechanisms, introduced in sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3
2. Stakeholders, introduced in section 4.2.4
3. Case examples matched to different instruments and mechanisms, of which a few example cases will be presented in Appendix 2: Case examples on blending financial mechanisms and instruments, and innovative financing solutions.

All modules are linked, but they can also be explored by users separately, i.e. at the search result (filtered list of solutions) users can see detailed information linked from the three modules. To understand the structure of the Guide, refer to Figure 13 below. The project team has set up the Guide's structure in Excel format. The team is in discussion with the UP2030 consortium for further development of the Guide into an interactive, web-based format. As of writing of this report, the functionalities and modules of the Guide are still under development, the target date for finalisation is by the end of 2025 (M36). An interim target date for fully developing Guide functionalities for testing by pilot cities is M22, when cities will be able to get to know and test the Guide in a dedicated workshop at the second UP2030 General Assembly (GenA).

Figure 13: Different modules of the Green Finance Guide and links between them

4.2.2 Classification of green financial and economic instruments and mechanisms

The Green Finance Guide lists existing financial and economic instruments and mechanisms for green projects. Moreover, the Guide lists bundles of financial and economic instruments that together serve as blended finance mechanisms that can leverage private sector finance.

The instruments and mechanisms included in the Guide are grouped according to the money's provenance - i.e., exclusively public (domestic and international), exclusively private, mixed (public and private), and own municipal revenues consisting of citizens' charges and taxes collected by local authorities-. It is important to highlight that transfers from higher-level governments are categorised as exclusively public instruments. Moreover, economic instruments are mainly categorised as municipal revenues. Distinguishing municipalities own source revenues (OSR) allows cities to identify financial instruments that can maximise their OSR beyond conventional options of increasing their billing and collection efficiency, using innovations, such as those in land value capture (LVC).

Moreover, instruments and mechanisms are sub-grouped by their need for repayment or, in other words, debt and equity instruments and their support to manage risks. Green finance is almost exclusively a debt market, where green bonds and loans such as sustainability-linked loans are the primary instruments used. In this context, emphasis is given to financial instruments and mechanisms that seek to increase the equity proportion of finance or encourage the strategic use of public funds and concessional

finance to mobilise significantly more private capital, which is imperative. The emphasis on these instruments is explored through the list of bundles of financial instruments. For example, bundles between EU grants and convertible bonds.

To facilitate financial innovation, the listed financial instruments and mechanisms are classified either as innovative or conventional from a city's perspective. For example, it is acknowledged that over 95% of green finance in Europe in 2021 came from green bonds issued by corporations (Breen, 2022). However, the utilisation of thematic bonds by cities is by far more mainstream. Thus, the criteria for classifying innovative vs. conventional instruments considers their level of utilisation by cities. The level of utilisation of each instrument was retrieved from CCFLA's Financial Instrument Toolkit taxonomy and NAP Global Network Inventory of Innovative Financial Instruments for Climate Change Adaptation. Innovative instruments are those categorised as either emerging when they have been tried and tested by cities or pilot, when there is limited evidence of their availability. In addition, conventional instruments are categorised as mature and are highly used by cities.

The listed financial instruments are classified by major sub-themes, although some instruments can be included in more than one theme:

- **Grants:** performance-based grants, capital grants, technical assistance grants, convertible grants, EU grants, sponsorships, donations.
- **Crowd financing:** online lending platforms, pre-sales crowdfunding models, and reward-based models.
- **Microfinance:** microcredits, micro-savings, micro-insurance, and microlending.
- **Thematic bonds:** municipal bonds, mini-bonds, green bonds, blue bonds, climate bonds, sustainability bonds, project bonds, general obligation bonds, catastrophe bonds or insurance pools, sustainability-linked bonds.
- **Loans and other debt financing instruments:** concessional loans, green loans, interest-free loans, sustainability-linked loans, syndicate loans, term loans, forgivable loans.
- **Equity financing:** private equity, viability gap funding, dedicated credit lines, green equity, equity futures, project-level equity.
- **Taxes and government transfers:** intergovernmental transfer, revenue support, ecological fiscal transfers (eft), leasing and asset financing models.

Similarly, the listed financial mechanisms are classified as:

- **Funds:** city climate funds, green investment funds, regional development funds, revolving funds, contingency and reserve funds, sovereign wealth funds, community fund, philanthropic funds.
- **PPP:** sell to a private partner and leaseback, concession to a private partner, management and 'operation and maintenance' contracts, leases and affermage contracts, concessions build-operate-transfer (bot) and design-build-operate projects, power purchase agreements for clean energy, project finance (SPVs), privatisation.
- **Energy performance contracts (EPC)** (a type of PPP): are agreements in which a range of services is outlined, and the service provider guarantees a minimum level of energy savings or sustainability outcomes. EPC – Guaranteed savings, EPC – Shared savings, EPC - Related payments, EPC - Immediate savings, EPC - Staggered savings.

- **Aggregation finance:** pooled procurement, pooled finance, aggregation platforms, asset-based securities or securitisation, energy services companies.
- **LVC:** Land banking and land readjustment, tax or fee-based LVC, development- LVC.
- **Carbon and other credit mechanisms:** city-based emissions trading systems (ETS) and carbon markets.
- **Leasing and asset finance models:** operating lease finance, hybrid models for purchase and lease of assets, internal contracting, energy efficiency obligation scheme, as-a-service models, pay-as-you-save), energy upgrade financing schemes, on-bill repayments, simple private contracting mode, vendor finance, model with forfeiting and waiver of defence.

Examples from economic instruments from the above categorisations can be identified under OSR from taxes and charges and LVC e.g., taxes, tax abatements for positive action or tax rebates on negative development aspects, charges and pricing for actions and services etc. The relationship between economic and financial instruments and mechanisms are explained in the box at the end of this section.

The Guide explores the complementarity between financial instruments to generate blended finance.

The utilisation of grants along with equity or debt instruments leads to three effects (FI Compass, n.d.):

1. **The revolving effect** - money repaid by final recipients can be reused to support further investments to support the program objectives.
2. **Leverage effect** - financial instruments can attract additional public and private co-investment to multiply the amount of financing available to final recipients. The scope to combine grants within the same operation further enhances the potential range of financial instruments.
3. **High impact** - Financial instruments are closer to the market and implemented by financial intermediaries who bring their own sector expertise. Thus, finance is targeted at viable projects with robust business plans, increasing the impact of the investments made.

Examples of financial instrument combinations included are EU grants plus partial self-finance, grants plus partial debt finance, etc.

Table 4 presents an example of the classification of financial instruments and mechanisms in the Guide.

Table 4: Example of financial measures classification from the Guide

Categories	Instrument	Non-repayable, repayable, de-risking	Source of funds
Taxes and Government Transfers	Municipal budget spending	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Taxes (property or business tax)	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Tax abatements for positive action	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Tax or rebates on negative development aspects	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Tax-line financing for clean energy and energy efficiency measures	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Charges and pricing for actions and services	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Intergovernmental transfer	Non-repayable	Public [Domestic]
	Revenue support	De-risking	Public
	Ecological fiscal transfers (EFT)	Non-repayable	Public
Carbon Credit Mechanisms	City-based emissions trading systems (ETS) and carbon markets	Non-repayable	Public
	Carbon credits from carbon markets (international or regional)	Non-repayable	Mixed
Land value capture (LVC)	Land banking and land readjustment	Non-repayable	Mixed
	Building rights and planning permits	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Development charges	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Land sales or auction	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Land or infrastructure asset leasing	Non-repayable	Municipal own source revenue (OSR)
	Tax or fee-based land value capture (LVC)	Non-repayable	Public
	Development-based land value capture (LVC)	Non-repayable	Public
Funds	Green investment funds	Repayable	Mixed
	City climate funds	Repayable	Mixed
	Regional development funds	Repayable	Public [International]
	Risk insurance products	De-risking	Risk management
	Currency exchange funds	De-risking	Risk management
	Revolving funds	Repayable	Mixed
	Contingency and reserve funds	De-risking	Mixed
	Sovereign Wealth Funds	Repayable	Public
	Philanthropic Funds	Non-repayable	Private
	Community fund	Non-repayable	Private
Grants	Recoverable grants	Non-repayable	Private
	Performance-based grants	Non-repayable	Public
	Capital grants	Non-repayable	Public
	Technical assistance grants	Non-repayable	Public
	Convertible grants	Non-repayable	Public
	EU grants	Non-repayable	Public
	Donations	Non-repayable	Mixed
	Sponsorship	Non-repayable	Private

Relationship between financial and economic instruments and mechanisms

The Green Finance Guide place particular attention in the interaction between economic and financial instruments and mechanisms. This is because, the interlinkage between financial instruments and economic incentives is key to maximizing private finance for a green transition (Ferri et al., 2019). Economic instruments seek to correct policy or/and market failures and reflect social costs or benefits by changing the behaviour of stakeholders. For example, market signalling through green taxonomies and corporate sustainability transparency requirements demonstrates how governments direct private finance. Economic instruments include traditional fiscal instruments, such as subsidies, taxes, charges, and fiscal transfers; instruments, such as tradable pollution permits or tradable land development rights; and instruments representing conditional and voluntary incentive schemes, such as payments for ecosystem services. Financial instruments, in contrast, are often extra-budgetary, such as foreign aid, external borrowing, debt for nature swaps, etc. (IPBES, 2022). When coordinated, economic and financial instruments can effectively leverage private finance.

For example, the Brazilian Forest Code promotes agroforestry by mandating a minimum of 20% to 80% natural vegetation on farmland. This regulation already re-directs agricultural investments towards agroforestry solutions to reach the vegetation target. However, the government and other development agencies can further incentivise private investment in agroforestry by reducing the costs and/or risks for private entities through blended finance instruments. For example, concessional and sub-ordinate loans, credit guarantees, and grants that use public capital (domestic public funding or ODA) can be used to catalyse private investment in activities that the investors would otherwise consider too risky or unfamiliar (UNEP, 2023).

4.2.3 Filtering of green financial instruments and mechanisms

To provide municipalities with a semi-tailored solution that considers the context of the green projects, the Guide allows filtering of the financial instruments and mechanisms based on four criteria:

1. **Climate objective** supported by the investment or project i.e., climate mitigation, climate adaptation, or both.
2. **Economic sector:** transportation and mobility; infrastructure; buildings and energy efficiency; energy generation and systems; water, waste and wastewater; urban development and management; green spaces and nature-based solutions; disaster risk management.
3. **EU taxonomy sector:** climate change mitigation, climate change adaptation, sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, transition to a circular economy, pollution prevention and control, protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.
4. **Project readiness and risk level**, combined into one project risk-readiness filter:

4.A. The Guide allows users to self-assess, in a fast and high-level manner, the investment readiness of their projects considering two criteria: degree of bankability of the project and project readiness. These two criteria will help users classify their projects as low, medium, or high readiness. Refer to Table 5 to review the assessment sub-criteria and qualification.

4.B. Project risk level: A fundamental investment principle is the relationship between investment risk and return. Different types of financial instruments and mechanisms are available based on the project risks. Therefore, it is essential for municipalities to self-assess the main types of project risks: operational, market and economic, financial risks, regulatory, legal and policy, technological, environmental, social, and governance. The Guide helps users categorise their projects as low, medium, or high risk. Refer to Table 5 to review the assessment sub-criteria and qualification.

By determining the aforementioned filters, the Guide provides a list of suitable financial instruments and mechanisms. In addition, the self-assessment conducted by users to determine the filter 4 allows municipalities to identify current and potential challenges, ensuring better project planning and execution (refer to Table 5 to guidance on self-assessment scoring). The Guide also provides a list of stakeholders that can help municipalities reduce their project risks or increase their project readiness through technical assistance (to be explored further in section 4.2.4). Moreover, to facilitate the use of the Guide to municipality actors who have a limited understanding of financial instruments and are more concerned about climate impacts can filter financial measures and their corresponding case examples based on the following characteristics: 1. Climate objective, 2. Economic sector and 3. EU taxonomy sector.

Table 5: Readiness and risk assessment guide with scores

CRITERIA	Low risk, high readiness = 1 point	Medium risk and readiness = 2 points	High risk, low readiness = 3 points
A. Project readiness			
Degree of bankability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High probability of meeting the project's financial, environmental, and social goals Sufficient estimated cash flows to cover costs and produce returns that meet investor expectations Project is implemented by a creditworthy entity Financing the scale-up of a tested solution or technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate probability of meeting financial, environmental, and social goals Reasonable but uncertain cash flows, capable of covering costs Implemented by an entity with moderate creditworthiness, possibly needing additional guarantees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low probability, and high uncertainty of meeting financial, environmental, and social goals Insufficient or highly uncertain cash flows, unable to cover costs reliably Implemented by an entity with low creditworthiness, lacking necessary guarantees Most likely a pilot project
Project readiness (development phase, technology readiness level (TRL) (European Commission, 2015), (Green Finance Institute , 2024))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a governance structure in place Legal contracts have been established 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a Business Case and Financial Model available for the projects There is a Baseline and Estimate for the project impacts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial Project Scoping phase with pre-feasibility studies Main stakeholders are identified

CRITERIA	Low risk, high readiness = 1 point	Medium risk and readiness = 2 points	High risk, low readiness = 3 points
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investors have been identified and contact High municipality capacity to undertake administrative tasks of financing a project TRL 7-9, equal to maturity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> supported by feasibility studies Main stakeholders are identified and engaged with Low municipality capacity to undertake administrative tasks of financing a project TRL 4-6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low municipality capacity to undertake administrative tasks of financing a project TRL 1-3, equal to research
B. Project risks			
Operational risks (UNDP, 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low complexity: straightforward processes Small-scale maintenance issues, potential failures that can be quickly resolved without significantly affecting the overall project performance Low exposure and vulnerability to climate change impacts High operational and organisational efficiency Low OPEX 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately complex processes Failures could lead to moderate operational disruptions and financial losses Ongoing maintenance for green infrastructure or technology might be more complex or expensive than initially planned Some organisational inefficiencies may occur (e.g. lack of central coordination team for projects, responsibilities are dispersed across the organisation) Medium OPEX 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High degree of vulnerability to climate change impacts of the targeted project Failures could lead to significant operational disruptions and financial losses High exposure to severe weather events, climate change impacts, that can cause significant damage to physical infrastructure, leading to costly repairs and downtime Mismanagement of project funds is highly probable High OPEX
Market and economic risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low fluctuation in commodity prices, interest rates and exchange rates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changes in commodity prices, interest rates and exchange rates impact project economies (costs and revenues) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High market and commodity price volatility, susceptibility to recession and downturn

CRITERIA	Low risk, high readiness = 1 point	Medium risk and readiness = 2 points	High risk, low readiness = 3 points
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some sectors are more exposed to market risks such as electric vehicles, or clean energy
Financial risks (World Bank, 2021)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Short payback period <5 years Low CAPEX, upfront costs needed – easier to obtain funding, financing Revenue generating project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medium payback period, 5-15 years Medium CAPEX, upfront costs Low profit is expected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Long payback period >15 years High CAPEX, upfront costs – large upfront costs of the project perceived as higher risks by investors Lack of revenue generation, profitability of the project
Regulatory, legal and policy risks (UN, 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changes in government regulations and policies are likely to have a low impact on profitability and attractiveness of project. Low probability of unfavourable regulation changes Clear and supportive regulations specifically encouraging urban climate action projects can streamline permitting processes and reduce regulatory risks overall Strong contractual agreements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Possibility of political events or regulatory changes that can lead to temporary disruptions but are unlikely to result in major policy shifts Slow permitting process, that can potentially delay project start dates and impact construction schedules Contractual disputes may occur 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High possibility of regulatory or policy changes that can undermine the business case for the project (e.g. withdrawal of subsidies and incentives, reversals in climate policies) Severe political instability, high levels of corruption Stringent permitting processes, challenging or impossible compliance requirements Land use disputes Incoherence of national or legal method of resolving disputes

CRITERIA	Low risk, high readiness = 1 point	Medium risk and readiness = 2 points	High risk, low readiness = 3 points
Technology risks (Georgiadis, 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well-established technologies Low probability of technical malfunctions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Material availability and construction challenges Technology used may not be commercially viable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complex infrastructure project Unproven, untested, cutting-edge technologies High exposure to supply chain disruptions Rapid advancement in sector may render technology obsolete
Environmental risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small scale project, limited physical investment No, or minor environmental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased resource use (e.g., energy and water consumption) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pollution, waste generation, biodiversity loss and habitat disruption and environmental degradation caused
Social risks (UNDP, 2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High social support Community involvement in planning and decision-making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited public participation Public, local community is informed Lack of understanding of project's benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong social resistance and opposition Concerns about the fair distribution of project benefits and burdens among different social groups Lack of social benefits identified
Governance risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong leadership and project management Minor procedural inefficiencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fragmented governance structure Moderate conflict of interests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weak institutional capacity Lack of transparency in operations

For simplicity, the Guide treats all risks equally, assuming that risks and project readiness are relatively equally important for investors and finance providers.

In a separate "self-assessment" module, users can calculate their average score to get an overall risk score for the project they seek financing for: Average Score = Total Score / Number of Risk Factors.

Interpretation of the results according to self-scoring:

- Low Risk: Average score between 1 and 1.5
- Medium Risk: Average score between 1.6 and 2.5
- High Risk: Average score between 2.6 and 3

An example calculation for self-risk assessment can be seen on the figure below:

Figure 14: Example calculation and risk scoring

In the Guide all green finance instruments and mechanisms are linked to a risk-readiness level, thus users can align the target project's risk level with suitable funding sources. The table below summarises the different financing instruments and funding sources that are available for the different risk and readiness levels (high-medium-low).

Table 6: The main green finance instruments and mechanisms, and their relevance and applicability for different project readiness and risk levels

Low risk, high readiness projects	Medium risk and readiness projects	High risk, low readiness projects
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercial loans • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private Equity • Concessional loans • Public-private partnerships • Green bonds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • De-risking instruments • Grants • Municipality own source revenue • Guarantees • Crowdfunding • Philanthropy

4.2.4 Stakeholder assessment

While in the early days, the landscape of green finance consisted mainly of international climate funds aimed at mitigation and adaptation activities, it has developed into a broad and contested ecosystem with manifold actors, instruments, and high volumes of capital flowing through it (Cunha et al., 2021). The Guide supports the identification of green finance providers for cities as well as technical assistance providers to support green project development. Table 7 classifies and describes the stakeholders relevant to European countries in providing green finance. The collection of stakeholders excludes the inclusion of public actors that enable green finance through regulation, grants, and subsidies, such as treasuries, finance ministries, and similar institutions.

Table 7: Financial providers assessed in the Guide

Stakeholder type	Characteristics	Instruments	Relevance for green finance in cities	Stakeholder examples
<i>Public finance providers</i>				
Finance ministries and treasuries <i>National</i>	Mobilisation and provision of green finance, regulatory power, increasing international coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxes and tax breaks • Subsidies • Grants • Technical and political support for finance mobilisation 	Moderate through regulation, high through active provision of green finance	<i>Relevant national ministries focusing on climate action (Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Finance, etc.)</i>
Public Development Banks (PDB) <i>Local, national</i>	Long-term developmental projects, climate finance, policy-driven	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct loans • Equity investments • Grants 	Moderate-High: Significant impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austrian Development Bank (OEBK) • French Development Agency (AFD)

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> German Credit Institute for Reconstruction (KfW)
Climate Funds <i>International</i>	<p>Funds or another investment vehicle that will only invest in com or projects that are deemed socially conscious and directly support climate mitigation and/ or adaptation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grants Low-interest loans Technical assistance Capacity building Project preparation support 	<p>Moderate-High: Significant national impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green Climate Fund (GCF) GIZ
Multilateral Development Banks <i>International</i>	<p>Provide financial and technical support to developing countries to help them strengthen their economies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low-interest loans Grants Guarantees Equity investments. 	<p>Low to Moderate</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Investment Bank (EIB) European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) - relevant for Spain and Portugal only
State-controlled programs <i>International</i>	<p>Bilateral lending, targeted climate initiatives, flexible and specialised through ODA programs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grants Low-interest loans Technical cooperation 	<p>Moderate: Targeted, specialised impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International Climate Finance Initiative (ICF) (UK) Germany's International Climate Initiative (IKI) (Germany) Joint Crediting Mechanism (JCM) (Japan)
Central Banks <i>National, transnational</i>	<p>Monetary policy, 'greening' operations, both public and private capital-facing, regulatory influence</p>	<p>Economic incentive to financial sector:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monetary policy Reserve requirements 	<p>High: Pervasive influence on (global) financial system</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Central Bank (ECB) Countries' central banks (e.g. Central

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bond purchases • Guarantees 		Bank of Hungary ⁴⁾
Municipal government <i>City-level, regional, international</i>	Financed projects with own revenue sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal climate funds 	High: significant local impact	<i>Local municipalities</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • London Green Fund (UK) • Paris Green Fund (France)
European Commission <i>International</i>	Provides support investment funds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grants (full and co-financing) 	High: significant sources of funding to cities, through various programmes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission (e.g. Horizon Europe; LIFE)
<i>Private finance providers</i>				
Large Asset Managers <i>Transnational</i>	Large volume of green assets, market discourse shaping, varying commitment to ESG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equity funds • Bond funds • Exchange traded funds (ETFs) 	High: Significant assets under management ⁵⁾	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BlackRock, Inc. • The Vanguard Group • State Street Corporation • Fidelity Investments
Private Domestic Commercial Banks (Akomea-Frimpong et al., 2021) <i>National, international</i>	Mediating function, underwriting green bonds, the potential for multiplying existing green finance flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loans • Green bonds • Depository receipts 	Moderate-Low: Conditional influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BNP Paribas (France) • HSBC (UK) • Deutsche Bank (Germany) • Santander (Spain) • ING (Netherlands) • Credit Agricole (France)
Insurance companies <i>National, international</i>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk insurance products 	Moderate-Low: Conditional influence, mainly in adaptation projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AXA • Allianz • Zurich Insurance Group

⁴ The Central Bank of Hungary (MNB) has launched its Green Program in 2019 to mitigate the risks associated with climate change and other environmental problems, to expand green financial services in Hungary, to widen the related knowledge base in Hungary and abroad, and to reduce financial market participants' and its own ecological footprint.

⁵ Access to private finance is critical, particularly as there is excess capital in global financial markets looking for suitable infrastructure projects, with a steadily growing interest from the private sector in city-level projects (Gorelick & Walmsley, 2020).

Venture Capital <i>National, international</i>	Provision of high-risk equity financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equity financing 	Moderate: focused impact to leverage equity finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EIT InnoEnergy Norrskan VC Ponooc VC
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The Green Finance Guide also identifies stakeholders that support the development of bankable projects. Developing bankable, climate-smart infrastructure projects requires skills and expertise not immediately available within municipal administrations. The most practical solution, therefore, for most cities and potential financiers is to work with Project Preparation Facilities (PPFs) that can provide a range of support in preparing a suitable investment proposal for a project, both helping to advise on the shaping of the project to improve its suitability for financing and work with potential investors to ensure the appropriate financing mechanisms are created. A few examples of city-focused PPFs working in Europe are:

- The EU and the European Commission provide support through a wide range of funding programmes, covering funding opportunities as well as advice on how to access funding and implementation. The Commission provides grants (full and co-financing) and technical assistance through a wide range of financing instruments and programmes, such as the Horizon Europe, LIFE and INTERREG programmes. The various funding opportunities European cities can access are available on the European Commission's website: https://commission.europa.eu/eu-regional-and-urban-development/topics/cities-and-urban-development/funding-cities_en.
- The EBRD provides project investment (loans, equity investments, guarantees, etc.), technical assistance, institutional capacity-building, and policy advisory services, with a regional emphasis on Central Asia, the southeastern Mediterranean, and Eastern Europe. EBRD's Sustainable Energy Initiative (SEI), provides financing and capacity development to develop local infrastructure projects in Eastern Europe, the Mediterranean and neighbouring regions. The sustainability and climate impact/vulnerability of projects is considered within the context of the economic transition of the wider region. In addition, the EBRD Green Cities program provides technical assistance to develop, implement and monitor action plans and stimulate green investments.
- The EIB funds a wide range of projects, including renewable energy, energy efficiency, sustainable transport, and climate adaptation. The EIB utilises various financial instruments, such as loans, equity investments, and green bonds, while collaborating with EU institutions, international organisations, and the private sector.
- The Global Infrastructure Facility (GIF), an initiative the World Bank, established in 2015, aims to increase the number of bankable infrastructure projects with a focus on complex projects with strong potential for private sector financing and focused advisory.

Table 8: Institutions providing finance and/or technical assistance (TA)

Stakeholder type	Stakeholder name	TA only	TA & finance	Relevant programs for European cities
Development Institutions	C40		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclusive Climate Action (ICA) fund to enable cities to unlock financial buy-in for inclusive climate action. Cities Finance Facility (CFF) facilitates access to finance for climate change mitigation and

Stakeholder type	Stakeholder name	TA only	TA & finance	Relevant programs for European cities
				resilience projects in urban areas by providing technical assistance to develop cities' sustainability priorities into bankable investment proposals – available for cities located in eligible for official development assistance according to the OECD DAC list (OECD, 2024) - hence only relevant for cities in Western Balkans and Turkey.
	ICLEI	X		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformative Actions Program (TAP) supports cities with their project pipeline and preparation, turning sustainable infrastructure ideas into investment ready projects.
	GIF		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GIF is providing end-to-end advisory services to client governments and multilateral development bank partners.
	World Bank	X		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City Creditworthiness Initiative supports cities to achieve higher creditworthiness and improve demand and supply side of financing by supporting project development and engaging with private sector investors • City Resilience Program supports risk-informed urban planning, identifies investments that enhance city resilience, and facilitates access to financing to ensure that those investments materialise
	Climate-KIC	X		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City Finance Lab helps to develop innovative financing solutions for cities.
	Cities Climate Finance Leadership Alliance	X		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotes project-level collaboration between CCFLA members to help them implement climate finance targets (Leadership for Urban Climate Investment).
Multilateral Development Banks (MDBs)	EIB		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical assistance for energy efficiency and renewable energy investments (ELENA). • Early-stage technical assistance for low-carbon, climate-resilient urban development plans and projects (City Climate Finance Gap Fund). • Through the Municipal Framework Loans, the EIB provides loans to finance projects and

Stakeholder type	Stakeholder name	TA only	TA & finance	Relevant programs for European cities
				technical assistance during the preparatory phase.
	EBRD		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The EBRD Green Cities provides technical assistance to develop, implement and monitor action plans and stimulating green investments.
	Development Bank of Latin America and Caribbean		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relevant for only Spain and Portugal. Operation credit and nonrefundable resources and technical support in structuring financial public and private projects.
Funds	GCF		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green Cities Facility (EBRD serves as accredited agency) provides grants, (concessional) loans, TA to Eastern European cities in target countries (Albania, North Macedonia, Moldova and Serbia)
	Climate Investment Fund		X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Technical Assistance Facility (TAF) helps attract and accelerate clean energy investments and de-risk the sustainable energy sector in developing countries, so they can move towards a green future. Clean Technology Fund (CTF) and the Strategic Climate Fund (SCF) are only accessible through the MDBs⁶
	City Climate Gap Fund	X		Gap Fund is project preparation fund to support cities in developing and emerging economies. Only Western Balkan and Turkish cities are eligible.
European Union	European Commission		X	Wide-range of technical assistance during different project stages (e.g. Horizon Europe, LIFE, eeef-TAF, Covenant of Mayors, InvestEU Advisory Hub (European Commission, 2024))

⁶ At the time of writing this report the TAF and the Funds are only available for Ukraine, Serbia, North Macedonia and Turkey)

4.3 Limitations of the Green Finance Guide

- **The Guide does not consider the city's environmental regulations for green investments.** Environmental-related regulations play a guiding and regulating role in the development of green finance and, to a certain extent, encourage green finance (Wang, 2017). (In order words, the governance of green finance is shaped by the structures it is embedded in)
- **The Guide does not consider the city's financial environment, including Institutional and legal frameworks, the City's financial health and sources of finance, expenditures, institutional and legal frameworks, Government structure, Decree, and the quality of interactions among government entities at different levels.**
- **The Guide does not showcase mechanisms/ instruments to improve the city's creditworthiness, transparency, and fiscal management.**
- **The Guide is unsuitable for designing tailored made financial solutions that specifically address all needs of the recipient or structuring finance for specific projects.** The combination of financial instruments - in coordination with the existing regulation- may answer specific investment projects' financial needs, such as a longer payback period as compared to market standards or an insufficient profitability level in view of market funding costs. The combination of financial instruments may also trigger the development of specific delivery modes or funding structures, which would crowd in more private money in particular sectors.
- **The Guide's risks and readiness self-assessments and matching recommendations are oversimplified and do not fully capture the complexity and interdependencies of real-world risks.** The scoring system for risks and readiness criteria is subjective, leading to bias and inconsistency. Different evaluators might score the same risk differently. Moreover, the importance of different risk factors can vary greatly depending on the specific context and type of project. Treating all risks as equally important oversimplifies the assessment and makes it impossible to reflect the true impact of different risks.
- **The actual availability of certain types of financing is influenced by broader market and economic conditions, trends, and local contexts.**

To partially address these limitations, the Guide provides case examples of innovative financial structures/ models as well as examples of the use of combined financial instruments with economic incentives to showcase real-life examples.

4.4 Expected outputs, outcomes and impact from the Green Finance Guide

The following table summarises the solutions offered by the Green Finance Guide: functionalities, outcomes, and impact of the tool, which addresses the cities' needs and gaps in terms of scaling climate finance.

Table 9: Green Finance Guide's functionalities, outputs, outcomes and expected impact

Status of development	Functionalities within the Green Finance Guide	Output of the functionality	Outcome	Expected impact
Developed	Interactive search of conventional and innovative (emerging and pilot) financial instruments, which can be filtered based on the relationship between the instrument and project risk and readiness, economic sector, financial instrument and mechanism classification (refer to sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A list of suitable financial instruments and mechanisms. 2. Linked case examples to financial instruments and mechanisms on successful application. 	<p>Cities can better navigate the financial landscape, overcome existing barriers to lack of funding, and make focused efforts to effectively mobilise resources and sources of green finance.</p> <p>Increase the utilisation of innovative financial instruments and strategies for green projects from European cities.</p>	Scale-up green finance for cities in the short to medium-term
In progress	<p>Interactive search of case examples, which can be filtered based on climate objective, project risk level, economic sector, etc.</p> <p>Interactive search on financial stakeholders that provide technical assistance.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Case examples for measures – the target is to have one per instrument depending on the availability studies (see example in Appendix 2: Case examples on blending financial mechanisms and instruments, and innovative financing solutions). 2. A list of stakeholders that provide technical assistance to cities for project development (refer to section 4.2.4). 	<p>Inform the development of a bankable and investor-ready pipeline of green projects.</p>	
In progress	Interactive search of financial instruments, which can be filtered	1. A list of financial arrangements or bundles of financial	Leverage private finance	

Status of development	Functionalities within the Green Finance Guide	Output of the functionality	Outcome	Expected impact
	based on project risk and readiness, and financial instrument classification.	instruments in which both conventional and innovative financial instruments, (as well as economic instruments that are a type of financial instruments), are used in conjunction to achieve blended finance. 2. One case example for each financial arrangement depending on availability.		Scale-up green finance for cities in the short to medium-term
To be developed	Interactive search on financial stakeholders that can be filtered based on the type of finance provided (refer to section 4.2.4).	1. A list of stakeholders (where meaningful) that provide finance to cities for project development finance to cities	Provide information on available funding and financing providers and promote engagement with private sector and finance providers stakeholders.	

4.5 Next steps

As of reporting on the work progress, the following work remains to be done:

- Testing the Guide with cities at workshop to be held at the second UP2030 GenA in 2024 October 15-17 (M22).

Further development tasks:

- In relation to the content of the Guide:
 - Linking stakeholders to financial instruments and mechanisms,
 - Linking innovative and blending case examples to financial instruments and mechanisms,
 - Refinement and amendment based on feedback received from testing with cities at the second GenA,

- Identify solutions, functionalities in the Guide that can support European cities in developing a bankable and investor-ready pipeline of green projects by improving coordination between environmental, financial, and city planning departments.
- In relation to achieving an interactive, web-based format for the Guide:
 - Development of excel based Guide to be ready for web-side based solution,
 - Integrating the Guide to T5.2 Replication and Transferability Packages, Service platform,
 - Development of user manual for online guide.

5 Cost-benefit analysis

5.1 Introduction to CBA

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is a key instrument to guide policymakers in their decision-making. By identifying the direct and indirect costs and benefits of a policy or investment project, governments and municipalities can assess whether the expenses are justified by benefits outweighing costs. In the opposite case, if the costs exceed the benefits, they can determine that proceeding would result in a loss of resources. Moreover, if there are limited resources facing multiple investment opportunities, the one with the highest net benefits (benefits minus costs) or the highest benefit to cost ratio (benefits / costs) shall be identified by conducting CBA. Whereas a private investor may only be interested in the costs and benefits that involve a cash flow, an extended socio-economic CBA also includes costs and benefits for members of society. Since CBA allows for including non-monetary benefits, it is particularly useful for projects with policy implications, notably at the city level. A municipality may aim to maximise environmental and health benefits through impacts such as reduced carbon emissions and air pollution. By identifying the most effective green investment projects, CBA helps attract green and climate finance, which provides a response to cities' financial constraints. Task 5.3 is focusing on CBA, as a main technique of economic assessment because, from a purely economic perspective, a CBA is preferred whenever possible with respect to the assessment of interventions enhancing climate resilience, an important benefit in urban context (GIZ, 2013). This has been reinforced through stakeholder consultations and GGGI's previous projects, where it was often observed that a gap exists between urban planners aiming for greening their cities and investors. Bridging this gap is essential for implementing more green projects and policies.

The next section reports on the project team's activities on CBA based on the cities' needs assessed in a survey (see above) and stakeholder consultation workshops presented in section 3.2 on UP2030 pilot city needs. After providing some methodological background on CBA, the section presents a status update on the development of the CBA user guide, which the project team considers as the suitable response to cities' stated needs as well as gaps in capacity and knowledge.

5.2 How to calculate the costs and benefits of a project

CBA can be conducted at the level of a specific infrastructure project as well as on investments or policies at a community, city, or national level. While the degree of detail regarding the cost and benefit components included may differ, the basic methodological principles are the same for any type of CBA. As explained above, a CBA intends to compare costs and benefits to assess whether an investment or policy pays off. Depending on the scope of the CBA, it may focus on monetary aspects only or also include non-monetary aspects. For a private investor, only direct cash flows may be relevant. However, for a public entity such as a municipality, money may be relevant directly (e.g. investment and cost savings) and indirectly (e.g. impact on tax revenues). Moreover, non-monetary benefits of a project such as improved air quality, better health, and emission reduction can be significant even if they are not expressed in money units and therefore have to be estimated. CBA thus gives the user a chance to apply a comprehensive perspective on costs and benefits, thus supporting informed decision-making to the benefit of the people affected.

In addition to comparing costs and benefits to each other, they are also compared to themselves over time. The concept of the time value of money (see for example (Croome, 2024)) states that 1 Euro today is worth more than 1 Euro next year because a) humans value the present higher than the future, thus

indicating time preference, and b) money can be invested in a risk-free asset such as a government bond, which will yield a return next year. From such a perspective, 1 Euro today is equivalent to 1 Euro plus annual return next year. Therefore, the further away in the future a monetary value, the less it is worth in terms of today's monetary units. The time value of money is reflected in the so-called **discount rate** (see for instance (Caplin & Leahy, 2004)), which is an interest rate that shall reflect the relationship of value across years. It can be set according to market interest rates but also according to social considerations. To express an amount of money in the future in terms of the present, it is divided by the term $(1 + \text{discount rate})^{\text{number of years in the future}}$. For CBA, this implies that costs and benefits in the future are less important than those in the present. Usually, this is particularly for the benefit side since benefits often take time to materialise whereas the investment costs occur in the present. Applying the discount rate thus tends to make estimates of net benefits conservative. Obviously, there is not one single appropriate discount rate. Where to set it has been subject to extensive debate in the academic literature (Burgess & Zerbe, 2015) Sensitivity analysis by varying discount rate assumptions can be useful to reflect the uncertainty in CBAs.

On the costs side, identifying the relevant components is often straightforward, especially when the CBA is conducted at the project level where the relevant expenses have been budgeted. It is important to distinguish between capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operational expenditures (OPEX). The former is, simply speaking, usually a one-time expenditure reflecting the investment made at the beginning of a new project. OPEX, on the other hand, consists of operation and maintenance costs and appears regularly once the project has entered its operation. Depending on the nature of a project, OPEX also includes capital depreciation, which allows for renewal of the invested capital and ensures its continued operation.

On the side of benefits, there are multiple categories ranging from aspects of health, environment, different types of cost savings, and economic as well as social impacts at a larger scale. Whereas monetary data on cost savings is often available, the non-monetary benefits need to be translated into monetary terms if they are to be fully included in the CBA.⁷ There are several methods to do this (GGGI, CEDS & EEI-Indonesia, 2018): 1) data collection to assess people's preferences or their willingness to pay for a certain benefit; 2) using market prices of related goods as proxies; or 3) estimating replacement costs or reparation costs of an asset, thus expressing the cost saved due to avoided damage. For many CBAs, users may not have the resources to collect data or apply complicated econometric techniques. Therefore, it can be helpful to take existing data and to apply them to the specific context. Sometimes, some adjustments to the data are needed, such as accounting for inflation or differences in income levels between the data source and the place of current application. For instance, the higher income and living standards in a place, the higher environmental impacts on infrastructure tend to be because the latter is most likely more expensive. The intention is to express benefits as appropriately as possible in line with the price and income levels of the local context.

5.3 Existing tools

There are a considerable number of CBA tools that apply to the context of European cities. They have been developed by, among others, the New Climate Institute, International Institute for Sustainable Development, World Bank, C40 Cities network, and the International Finance Corporation (IFC). These tools support urban planners and policymakers in assessing projects in terms of their expected, or materialised, benefits, particularly the non-monetary ones.

⁷ Non-monetary values can always be expressed as such but they cannot be compared to the costs.

A lot of time and resources for methodological set-up of CBA, calculations, and data collection can be saved by using these readily available tools. While they expect inputs on project information and some context-related data, they can even be applied if city-level data is not available by resorting to pre-defined default data that the tools already contain. Instead of developing another tool, this project builds on and consolidates the currently available tools and knowledge.

The existing publicly available tools that the project has found to be relevant for the context of green urban planning are summarised in Table 10.

Table 10: Overview of CBA tools considered

#	Tool name	Developed by	Sectoral focus	Climate focus
1	AQUA: Air Quality through Urban Actions	C40 Cities network	Agriculture, buildings, industry, transport	Mitigation
2	Climate Opportunity Interactive Dashboard	C40 Cities network, New Climate Institute, Bloomberg Philanthropies	Energy, transport, buildings	Mitigation
3	CRC: Climate Resilient City Tool	Deltares	Buildings, urban parks	Adaptation
4	CURB: Climate Action for Urban Sustainability	World Bank	Transport, buildings, waste management, energy	Mitigation and adaptation
5	Cycling and Walking Assessment Tool	C40 Cities network	Transport (walking and cycling)	Mitigation
6	EDGE: Excellence in Design for Greater Efficiencies	IFC	Buildings	Mitigation
7	Equitable Impacts toolbox: Bus Rapid Transit Systems	C40 Cities network	Transport	Mitigation
8	Equitable Impacts toolbox: Congestion Pricing	C40 Cities network	Transport	Mitigation
9	Equitable Impacts toolbox: Cool Roofs	C40 Cities network	Buildings	Mitigation
10	Equitable Impacts toolbox: Waste Collection & Segregation	C40 Cities network	Waste management	Mitigation
11	Gi Hub Tool for bus projects	Deloitte	Transport	Mitigation
12	Heat Resilient Cities Tool	C40 Cities network	Urban parks, urban water, cool surfaces, heat action plans	Adaptation

#	Tool name	Developed by	Sectoral focus	Climate focus
13	HEAT: Health economic assessment tool	World Health Organization (WHO)	Transport	Mitigation
14	HERB: Healthy and Efficient Retrofitted Buildings Tool	C40 Cities network	Buildings	Mitigation
15	MICAT: Multiple Impact Calculation Tool	Fraunhofer ISI, IEECP, Wuppertal Institut	Agriculture, industry, construction, transport, residential	Mitigation
16	P-AQ: Pathways Air Quality	C40 Cities network	Buildings, waste management, energy, industry	Mitigation
17	SAVi: Sustainable Asset Valuation	International Institute of Sustainable Development	Transport, buildings, waste management, agriculture, industry, energy	Mitigation and adaptation
18	TRACE: Co-Benefits Evaluation Tool for the Urban Transport Sector	New Climate Institute, Initiative for Climate Action Transparency (ICAT)	Transport	Mitigation

These tools focus either on climate mitigation, adaptation, or both. They include sectors such as energy, transport, buildings, waste management, (urban) agriculture, industry, and urban parks. Moreover, there are particular aspects of climate adaptation such as creating green roofs and other cooling surfaces and heat management actions in urban areas. The tools vary considerably in terms of complexity as well as time and resource requirements for urban planners to apply them to their specific projects. Most of the inputs and dedication in the CBA process goes to the identification and estimation of benefits, notably the non-monetary ones. The more complex tools may include more benefit categories and/or assess them more accurately and specifically to the respective city context than the simpler tools.

Whereas many tools express all benefits in monetary terms, including those that are non-monetary in nature but translated into money units, some provide estimates in real terms such as, for instance, employment creation in number of jobs, time savings in hours, prevalence of diseases in number of cases, or particulate matter (PM) emissions. The most important and recurring benefits across tools are energy savings, health cost savings, impact on GDP, the estimated monetary value of human lives.⁸ As described in the previous section, a CBA in a strict sense intends to compare costs and benefits in monetary terms. However, urban planners and policymakers might also be interested in benefits estimated in real terms to support their decision-making.

⁸ The theoretical monetary value of a human life, despite the ethical controversies around it, is estimated by the so-called value of statistical life (VSL).

5.4 CBA Guide

Due to the considerable wealth of knowledge contained in various CBA tools, urban planners and policymakers struggle getting an overview and finding out about the tool that exist and which of them are suitable to their specific needs. This is why this project develops a guidance for cities to direct them to the appropriate CBA tool as well as any additional supporting documents and data sources. Hence, the main goal of this Guide is simplification to bring technical knowledge closer to CBA applicants.

The Guide shall identify the user's needs regarding technical aspects such as focus on sectors, climate mitigation or adaptation, and the type of benefits that are of interest to the user. Yet, in practice it is usually not simply the technical assessments that matter but also a user's resources and capacity to apply the tool. The most sophisticated CBA tool may never be used by a municipality if it is too complex and requires too much time, data, and financial resources compared to the municipality's needs and capacity. Therefore, some of the Guide's questions involve a needs assessment by asking the user how sophisticated the planned CBA shall be. Moreover, the Guide asks a question regarding data availability on the side of the user as well as about the intended resources in terms of times and/or days that the user plans to invest.

The Guide processes the inputted information as exhibited in Figure 15. It relates the information on the user's needs to the characteristics of the CBA tools to identify the most suitable tool(s). For instance, if the user wants to do a detailed CBA, the tools with higher complexity get a higher weight. Likewise, if the sector of interest transport, the Guide excludes all tools that do not offer CBA on transport projects or policies. Based on the needs assessment, the Guide identifies the tool with the highest number of points compared to the other tools and presents it as the first-best tool. This means that this is the most suitable tool if there are no resource constraints. In the next step, the Guide matches the estimated time and financial resources required for the application of each of the tools with the available resources as inputted by the user. Tools that exceed available resources drop out of the tool ranking. The Guide's the next result thus is the indication of the second-best tool, which respects the resource constraint. In case the latter is not binding, the first-best tool and the second-best tool are the same. In case they are different, the user gets helpful information on why the second-best tool was selected. By following the links to the tools provided by the guide, the user then can check the results and decide if investing more resources to make the first-best tool feasible is appropriate.

Finally, the Guide checks for the user's data gaps that make it difficult to possibly even apply the second-best tool. As a third result, the Guide provides links to relevant data sources that the selected second-best tool requires.

Figure 15: Structure of CBA guide

At this stage of development of the Guide, the following features are already there:

- As part of WP5 of UP2030, the project team conducted stakeholder workshops with city representatives to assess cities' needs as well as their constraints. It turned out that benefits in the areas of environment, health, and economic and social aspects have high importance. Moreover, lack of time and financial resources as well as technical capacity are all important constraints that must be addressed for cities to effectively conduct CBAs.
- The project team has set up the Guide's structure in Excel format. It includes the questionnaire (see Figure 16 below) and the corresponding dynamic dropdown menu for the user to choose the answers. Moreover, there is a tab where all CBA tools are characterised to assess their suitability depending on the user's needs.
- All CBA tools have been assessed at a preliminary level for their characteristics regarding sectoral focus, level of complexity, type, and number of benefits they analyse, and the data inputs they require.
- The logical flow of the Guide's questions, the user's responses, and the dropdown menu for answers is established. This involves aspects such as, for example, ensuring that the type of benefits available for the user to choose from to express preference is in line with the benefits the tools with the selected focus sector include. Therefore, the answer options change dynamically depending on the answers provided to the preceding questions.
- The draft algorithm to rank tools according to the answers provided is developed. This step involves some judgment of how several tool characteristics are weighed against each other, which defines which tools emerge as first-best and second-best.

Question	Answers												
What do you want to do?	Detailed CBA												
Are you interested in mitigation or adaptation projects?	Mitigation												
Which sector would you like to focus on in your activity?	Transport												
What benefits would you like to include in the CBA?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Health <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cost savings <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and social <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Air pollution</td> <td>GHG emissions</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Number of lives saved</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Air pollution	GHG emissions			Number of lives saved							
Air pollution	GHG emissions												
Number of lives saved													
What type of national or local data do you have available?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Population data (total, age distribution, income distribution)</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Climate data (precipitation, climate zone)</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Health data (prevalence of heart diseases, respiratory infections, diabetes, pulmonary diseases)</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Transport-related data (vehicle categories and emissions, shares of transport modes)</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	Population data (total, age distribution, income distribution)	Yes	Climate data (precipitation, climate zone)	No	Health data (prevalence of heart diseases, respiratory infections, diabetes, pulmonary diseases)	Yes	Transport-related data (vehicle categories and emissions, shares of transport modes)	Yes				
Population data (total, age distribution, income distribution)	Yes												
Climate data (precipitation, climate zone)	No												
Health data (prevalence of heart diseases, respiratory infections, diabetes, pulmonary diseases)	Yes												
Transport-related data (vehicle categories and emissions, shares of transport modes)	Yes												
What resources are you going to use for the activity?	Internal resources by dedicating staff time												
What is the amount of your resources available for the activity?	0-3 days												
First-best tool	C40 Pathways Air Quality (AQ)												
Second-best tool	Gi Hub tool for bus projects												

Figure 16: Questionnaire of the draft CBA Guide (with random answers)

5.5 Limitations of the CBA Guide

The CBA Guide simplifies cities' access to CBA support tools and, at the same time, creates awareness of the aspects that an urban planner needs to account for when doing CBA. This includes scenario building, the various types of benefits, and the meaning of discounting. While this is expected to remove a relevant barrier to using CBA, the Guide cannot rule out every challenge. When an urban planner applies the Guide, the suggested tools are those that suit her needs best, but this does not rule out some specific needs remaining unmet. For instance, the Guide user may want to assess benefits x, y, and z in a simple, high-level tool but it is only a sophisticated and complicated-to-use tool that includes those benefits. This potential shortcoming is because the CBA Guide builds on existing knowledge and cannot close the gaps that exist in the currently available tools.

Another limitation concerns the issue of economic valuation in general. CBA intends to quantify all costs and benefits in a way to make them comparable to each other. Yet, getting to those quantitative values often requires assumptions and, therefore, judgment. By introducing urban planners to CBA tools, the

Guide makes these assumptions either transparent or outsources them to the tools that urban planners choose to use. Yet, despite giving the impression of clear-cut calculations, CBA cannot do without judgment and therefore must deal with uncertainty and the risk of misinterpreting results. The CBA Guide helps make informed decisions but does not remove the need for careful interpretation of CBA results.

5.6 Expected outputs, outcomes and impact from the CBA Guide

Table 11: CBA Guide’s functionalities, outputs, outcomes and expected impact

Status of development	Functionalities within the CBA Guide	Output of the functionality	Outcome	Expected impact
Developed	Interactive search of CBA tools, which are selected based on the user's needs, including degree of detail, sectoral focus, climate focus, types of benefits (refer to section 5.4 of this report).	The CBA tool that suits the user's needs best is selected.	Cities use the CBA tools suitable to their needs thanks to improved access to existing tools to make informed decisions.	Increase in number of green urban projects and policies and thanks to (i) more efficient allocated resources, and (ii) increased project attractiveness through the comprehensive assessment of their costs and benefits.
In progress	Assessment of the user's available resources to conduct CBA and matching with the user's needs.	The CBA tool that suits the user's needs as much as possible while being aligned with the user's available resources is selected.	Cities use the CBA tools suitable to their available resources thanks to improved access to existing tools to make informed decisions.	
In progress	Identification of relevant data sources, guidance, and case studies for the tool selected.	Links to data sources, guidance, and case studies that are required or helpful for the tool selected are provided to the user.	Relevant data gaps are closed for cities to apply the CBA tools most suitable to their needs.	

5.7 Next steps

As of reporting on the work progress, the following work remains to be done:

- Testing the Guide with cities at workshop to be held at the second UP2030 GenA in 2024 October 15-17 (M22).
- The links to data sources to address the user's stated data gaps need to be included.
- Additional supportive documents such as methodological explanations and case studies (see for instance (GGGI, CEDS & EEI-Indonesia, 2018)) shall be provided as links jointly with data sources as part of the Guide's output.
- The calibration of some tool characteristics must be refined. For instance, the estimate of how much resources the application of each tool requires is only a rough guess so far. By getting in touch with tool developers, a more realistic estimate will be identified such that tools become comparable.
- The Guide needs to be applied to a sufficient number of internal tests runs to discover and eliminate any inconsistencies. The workshop with UP2030 cities in M22 may also reveal flaws to be corrected.
- The available tools appear to cover relevant sectors in a rather comprehensive way. As an exception, disaster management is an aspect that is only addressed partially. The project team will do more research to find existing methodology documents to suggest to the Guide users if this is their preferred focus.
- The project team will explore the options of converting the Excel format of the Guide to a web-based version to make access easier and more user-friendly.

6 Conclusion

The UP2030 project is taking significant steps in addressing the challenges that European cities face in implementing and upscaling their climate action initiatives. This report, within the context of WP5, underscores the importance of financing, and economic assessments in facilitating the transition towards climate-neutral and resilient urban environments.

Throughout this report, several key insights have emerged. First, cities are at the forefront of climate change impacts, and their role in mitigating these effects is paramount. However, the financial barriers they face—ranging from high upfront costs and regulatory constraints to the lack of technical capacity—are considerable. These barriers hinder cities' ability to access the necessary funds and effectively implement climate interventions. To overcome these barriers, the development of the Green Finance Guide and the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) Guide represents an important step forward. These tools are designed to equip cities with the knowledge and resources needed to navigate the landscape of green finance and evaluation of their climate initiatives.

The Green Finance Guide offers a comprehensive overview of available financial instruments and mechanisms that can be refined to high-level city contexts and needs, alongside providing information of relevant stakeholders for mobilising finance. By showcasing case studies and providing recommendations for blending various financial instruments, the Guide aims to empower cities to develop robust financial strategies that align with their climate goals.

The CBA Guide provides a structured approach for cities to assess the economic viability of their climate projects, emphasising both monetary and non-monetary benefits. The Guide simplifies the process of selecting and applying appropriate CBA tool for cities climate projects and investments.

The Guides are not just theoretical constructs but are grounded in the real needs and experiences of the UP2030 pilot cities. Through direct engagements with pilot cities, the project has identified the specific challenges that cities face. The Guides aim to address these challenges by equipping cities with the necessary tools to mobilise finance by identifying various sources of finance and to conduct thorough economic assessments.

As the project moves forward, the focus will be on further developing and refining these guides and finding ways for their integration into the UP2030 Service Platform, as interactive, web-based solutions. The anticipated workshop at the second UP2030 General Assembly in M22 will be pivotal for gathering further insights for refining and finalising these Guides.

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Appendix 1: Financing capacities and needs questionnaire sent to pilot cities

Table 12: Financing capacities and needs questions sent to UP2030 pilot cities

I. Identification	Type of question
1. City's name	Open ended
II. Budget planning and current financing capacities The aim of this section is to understand the city's financing position, support the analysis of historic and forecasted budgets. The section focuses on funding sources and whether the city's budget is linked to its climate action plan.	Type of question
2. How is the capacity of your city's budget to meet financial obligations is ensured?	Open ended
3. What is the level of debt in your city (for this survey please measure by <i>debt service coverage ratio = total income / debt interest + principal repayments in 2022</i>)?	Open ended
4. How sustainable is your level of debt?	Open ended
5. If debt is centrally regulated, has the government approved any access to credit in the past 5 years?	Yes / No
6. In relation to COVID 19 recovery expenditures, do you have any remaining debt related to green recovery measures?	Yes / No
7. What sources of funding do you generally rely on (public finance, equity or debt financing (e.g., grants, loans, private investment, public-private partnerships or innovative schemes and vehicles). Please select from the list below (more than one can be selected).	List (multiple choice): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxation • Land / infrastructure lease • Land sale • User charges and fees • Central government grants and subsidies • Other grants • Public-private partnerships • Equity funded direct (private) investment • Joint Ventures (JVs) • Special Purpose Vehicles (SPVs)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Loans (syndicated, concessional, soft Etc.) • Bonds (incl. municipal, green) • ESCO (energy efficiency projects) • Debt refinancing instruments • Voluntary carbon markets • Emission Trading Scheme • <i>Other</i>
8. If you selected "other", please list those other sources of financing.	Open ended
9. Are there any budget lines in your city's budget specifically dedicated to sustainable urban development and climate action?	Yes / No
10. Is your budget aligned with your city's climate strategy or SECAP ⁹ ?	<p>List (multiple choice):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. The objectives of the SECAP/ strategy are reflected in the budget. ii. Budgets allocated for the climate actions are included in the city's climate strategy. iii. None of the above.
11. Do you classify budget items from a climate perspective (e.g., budget items that are highly favourable, quite favourable, neutral, unfavourable from a climate mitigation and/or adaptation point of view)?	Yes / No
12. Do you have budget for contingencies related to negative climate induced disasters?	Yes / No
13. How does your city prioritize or rank large investment projects? Please name any tools used.	Open ended
14. What are the main funding sources for larger development projects?	Open ended
15. Have you previously received resources from any European Union Funding Programmes for urban development?	Yes / No
16. >>> If yes, name all EU Funding Programmes under which you received funds.	Open ended

⁹ Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan

<p>III. Estimating costs and benefits of climate action plans</p> <p>The aim of this section is to understand how your city assesses and quantifies the costs and benefits (including co-benefits) of climate action plans (projects, investments etc.).</p>	<p>Type of question</p>
<p>17. How do you estimate the costs of your city’s climate action plan, individual climate actions, sustainability projects? Please name any tools, methodologies used.</p>	<p>Open ended</p>
<p>18. How do you estimate the potential co-benefits (environmental, social, and other co-benefits) of your climate actions, such as job creation, economic development, and public health improvements? Please name any tools used (if any).</p>	<p>Open ended</p>
<p>19. Have you been able to quantify or monetise these benefits in the past?</p>	<p>Yes / No</p>
<p>20. Are there any business cases in your city where a climate project generates income?</p>	<p>Yes / No</p>
<p>21. >>> If yes, please provide an example.</p>	<p>Open ended</p>
<p>IV. Financing needs of the city’s climate action plans (climate strategy or SECAP) The aim of this section is to gain a general understanding of how your city can finance its climate action plan (i.e., all projects, investments etc.) and identify specific barriers and circumstances.</p>	<p>Type of question</p>
<p>22. What are the main financial challenges and barriers to implementing your climate action plan?</p>	<p>Open ended</p>
<p>23. Are there any national or local regulations that prevent your city from accessing certain types of financing (e.g., government-imposed limits on borrowing)?</p>	<p>Yes / No</p>
<p>24. >>> If yes, please elaborate.</p>	<p>Open ended</p>
<p>V. Financing needs and estimated benefits of your city’s pilot project</p> <p>The aim of this section is to understand financing needs of your pilot/neighbourhood demonstration project (i.e., the pilot project that your city is implementing under UP2030).</p>	<p>Type of question</p>
<p>25. How much funding or additional sources of finance do you estimate you will need to fully implement your pilot project? (If any.)</p>	<p>Open ended</p>
<p>VI. Other additional thoughts and comments</p>	<p>Type of question</p>
<p>26. (Optional) Anything else you would like to add, e.g.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financing needs and barriers in relation to your city’s pilot project? 2. Cost benefit analysis issues. 3. In light of the expected outcome of developing a financing toolkit and CBA toolkit what type of support do you expect? 	<p>Open ended</p>

Appendix 2: Case examples on blending financial mechanisms and instruments, and innovative financing solutions

1. Case example:

Residential energy efficiency instruments in Lithuania

Region	Europe
Country	Lithuania
City	multiple

Climate objective	Mitigation
Sector(s)	Buildings and energy efficiency
Financing instrument(s) and mechanism(s)	Combination of grants with financing instruments (including technical support, interest rate and guarantee fee subsidies, capital rebates)
Financing category(ies)	Grant, loans and guarantees
Financing source(s)	Public (national and international) and private
Year	2015-2023

Summary of description

Financial instruments, in combination with grants, have been used by Lithuania’s Ministry of Finance and Ministry of Environment to fund low cost, long term, low interest loans to residents to support investment in energy efficiency in apartment block buildings in Lithuania. Almost EUR 1 billion of funding was made up of EUR 250 million ERDF resources from the Operational Programme for EU Structural Funds Investments for 2014-2020 and up to EUR 705 million co-investment from financial intermediaries and third-party investors. The financial instruments have supported the development of a single product for homeowners known as the ‘Modernisation Loan’ which forms the centrepiece of the Lithuanian government’s programme to improve energy efficiency in residential properties. Grants are used in combination with the financial instruments to fund technical support, interest rate subsidies and capital rebates and a “one stop shop” service arrangement was also established that has been key to the successful delivery of the programme. At the end of the programming period, the financial instruments had financed the renovation of more than 1 000 buildings across Lithuania’s 60 municipalities.

Source	https://www.fi-compass.eu/library/case-studies/residential-energy-efficiency-financial-instruments-lithuania
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2. Case example

Cape Town Green Bond

Region	Africa
Country	South Africa
City	Cape Town

Climate objective	Mitigation and Adaptation
Sector(s)	Buildings and energy efficiency
Financing instrument(s) and mechanism(s)	Issuance of the bond, accreditation by the Climate Bonds Initiative, Moody's certification, technical assistance by the Cape Chamber of Commerce, listing the bond on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange
Financing category(ies)	Green bond
Financing source(s)	Private
Year	2017-2027

Summary of description

In 2017, amid a severe drought, Cape Town issued its first Green Bond, valued at ZAR1 billion, to fund sustainability projects aimed at climate change adaptation and mitigation. Accredited by the Climate Bonds Initiative (CBI) and rated GB1 (excellent) by Moody's, the bond was issued by Rand Merchant Bank, financed by international investors, and facilitated by the Cape Chamber of Commerce. The bond finances projects such as electric buses, energy efficiency in buildings, water resilience initiatives, sanitation treatment, and coastal protection. As the first of its kind in South Africa, the Green Bond demonstrated strong market confidence and set a high standard for transparency and reporting. It supports Cape Town's climate strategies, promotes environmentally responsible investment, and highlights the importance of effective governance and regular reporting to maintain investor trust and avoid greenwashing. This initiative provides a model for sustainable urban development and encourages the future issuance of green bonds.

Source	https://www.gihub.org/innovative-funding-and-financing/case-studies/cape-town-green-bond/
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3. Case example:

Contribution of carbon credits to pay for green transport improvements in Bucharest, Romania

Region	Europe
Country	Romania
City	Bucharest

Climate objective	Mitigation
Sector(s)	Transportation and mobility
Financing instrument(s) and mechanism(s)	City-based emissions trading systems (ETS) and carbon markets
Financing category(ies)	Carbon credit mechanisms
Financing source(s)	Private
Year	2013 -

Summary of description

Since 2013, Romanian industrial and power companies who entered the European Union Emissions Trading Scheme EU ETS in 2007 are required to buy rights to emit carbon dioxide. A carbon credit is a ‘right to pollute’ certificate that entitles the right to emit one tonne of carbon dioxide or the mass of another greenhouse gas, with a CO2 equivalent. The idea is to make it more expensive for power companies to emit, become energy efficient and switch to greener technologies. The carbon credits Romania system is fairly successful, with the implementation with highly polluting companies receiving 70% of carbon credits. The sale of carbon credits to Romanian power companies enabled financing of new developments such as 122km of cycling paths and 4 metro lines with 45 stations. This resulted in reduced usage of vehicles and related carbon emissions. 70% of the received income from carbon credits has been spent on climate investment projects by the government of Romania.

Source	https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/164441468184789255/pdf/103911-WP-P145943-PUBLIC-Dissemination-Note-ETS-Study.pdf https://citiesclimatefinance.org/financial-instruments/cases/contribution-of-carbon-credits-to-pay-for-green-transport-improvements-in-bucharest-romania
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4. Case example:

Combining private investment and an EIB loan to cope with water scarcity in Lisbon

Region	Europe
Country	Portugal
City	Lisbon

Climate objective	Adaptation
Sector(s)	Water, waste and wastewater management
Financing instrument(s) and mechanism(s)	Public loan, private financing
Financing category(ies)	Blended finance
Financing source(s)	Public and private
Year	2005 -

Summary of description

In Lisbon, the water company EPAL (Empresa Portuguesa das Águas Livres) found a way to reduce the volume of water lost as a result of leakages (also known as non-revenue water). The main source of this problem is linked to faults in the pipelines due to ageing infrastructure. To address the water leakages, EPAL decided to develop the monitoring programme WONE through which it can identify water leakages more quickly and locate them more precisely. It used its own budget. The monitoring system allows the comparison of expected water usage data with real-time water usage using tailor-made software. When a discrepancy is found, it alerts the monitoring team, which then identifies the leak by tracing back from the water meter that provided the data. After the location of the leak, leak detection mechanics carry out field-based leak detection and repair the damage.

To finance the infrastructure renewal, EPAL has received loans of almost EUR 2.5 billion from the EIB, at favourable interest rates, since 1993. It used the EIB support to finance water supply extensions and upgrades, waste management measures, sanitation networks and efficiency improvements. The programme has resulted in a reduction of non-revenue water from 23.5 % in 2005 to around 8.5 % in 2015.

Source	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/case-studies/private-investment-in-a-leakage-monitoring-program-to-cope-with-water-scarcity-in-lisbon
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5. Case example:

Stormwater credit trading program

Region	North America
Country	USA
City	Washington, D.C.

Climate objective	Adaptation
Sector(s)	Water, waste and wastewater management
Financing instrument(s) and mechanism(s)	Stormwater retention credit
Financing category(ies)	Credit mechanism
Financing source(s)	Private
Year	2013-

Summary of description

Development projects are required by the District of Columbia to retain 100% of the stormwater on their sites to avoid hazardous flooding. If all of the stormwater cannot be retained as required, developers can either pay a fee in lieu of the cost of implementing stormwater retention measures or they can buy stormwater credits as needed to keep their projects under the set limit. These credits are generated by other developers that construct stormwater management control structures (e.g., green roofs, rain gardens, permeable pavement, tree planting) in the district. Credits can be generated through actions taken on one property or aggregated from multiple properties.

The stormwater credit trading program of Washington, D.C. is an innovative climate program that increased climate resilience through green infrastructure that prevented flooding and reduced the urban heat island effect. Washington, D.C.'s credit market completed 44 trades in both the 2020 and 2021 fiscal years, with the value of credits traded in the two years totalling over USD 1,600,000. The program has encouraged the growth of green infrastructure investment, creating more green space and stormwater retention capacity.

Source	https://napglobalnetwork.org/innovative-financing/?category=results-based-financing&instrument=stormwater-credit-trading-program
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